

A Scale-Invariant Direct Multisearch Method for Mixed-Variable Multiobjective Optimization^{*}

J. F. A. Madeira

IDMEC–IST, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Av. Rovisco Pais, 1040-001 Lisboa, Portugal, and ISEL–IPL, Rua Conselheiro Emídio Navarro, 1, 1959-007 Lisboa, Portugal

Abstract

Many multiobjective optimization problems in computational operations research, simulation-based decision making, and engineering design involve black-box functions and decision variables of different types. Continuous variables have a natural local geometry, ordered discrete variables have an ordinal structure, and categorical variables are purely nominal. Applying direct-search ideas to such problems therefore requires a search geometry that is meaningful across variable types and insensitive to arbitrary choices of scaling, spacing, or labeling.

We propose DMS-SI-Mix, a deterministic direct multisearch framework for mixed-variable multiobjective derivative-free optimization. The method keeps the standard DMS mechanism of maintaining a nondominated list and selecting poll centers from that list, but performs polling in a canonical search space; objective functions are evaluated only after reconstruction in the original decision space. A single step-size parameter controls the continuous, ordered discrete, and categorical poll moves, with a common fraction-of-domain interpretation across variable types. This separation makes the canonical search trajectory invariant under representation changes that carry no algorithmic information: affine rescaling of continuous variables, numerical spacing of ordered discrete variables, and arbitrary relabeling of categorical variables.

The convergence analysis is deliberately local and conditional. Under the stated assumptions and along refining subsequences, accumulation points satisfy a mixed-block Pareto stationarity condition: Pareto–Clarke stationarity along the continuous polling directions, together with weak local Pareto optimality on the ordered discrete and categorical blocks, each expressed in its native geometry.

Computational results illustrate the practical effect of the canonical formulation. On continuous benchmark problems with heterogeneous scaling, and on an engineering piezo-shunt design problem, the scale-invariant formulation yields statistically significant improvements over Direct Multisearch under heterogeneous scaling, while behaving comparably under uniform scaling. On controlled mixed-variable benchmark pairs, the method preserves meaningful Pareto-front structure after reformulation, with problem-dependent degradation when the finite blocks restrict the attainable front. The resulting framework provides a simple and reproducible way of extending direct multisearch to heterogeneous decision spaces without imposing a global metric on them.

Keywords: derivative-free optimization, multiobjective optimization, direct multisearch, scale invariance, mixed-variable optimization, categorical variables, deterministic neighborhood rotation, Pareto–Clarke stationarity
2020 MSC: 90C29, 90C56, 65K05, 90C30

1. Introduction

Many optimization problems in engineering design and simulation involve several conflicting objectives, evaluated by numerical models for which derivatives are unavailable, unreliable, or expensive. In such settings the objectives are

^{*}The author acknowledges the support of Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT), Portugal, through IDMEC, under LAETA, project UID/50022/2025.

Email address: aguilarmadeira@tecnico.ulisboa.pt (J. F. A. Madeira)

naturally treated as black boxes, and derivative-free methods are the appropriate tool. Direct-search methods of directional type address this case without derivatives, and Direct Multisearch (DMS) [1, 2] extends them to multiobjective optimization: rather than a single iterate, DMS maintains a list of nondominated points, polls around a point selected from that list, and uses Pareto dominance—not a scalar merit function—to decide whether new points are accepted. An iteration is successful when the list changes. DMS does not aggregate the objectives and aims to approximate the whole Pareto front.

In its standard form, DMS operates on continuous variables. Many design problems, however, mix variables of different kinds: continuous parameters, ordered discrete choices such as gauge numbers or component counts, and categorical configurations such as material types or topological layouts. These three kinds of variables do not share a geometry. Continuous variables carry a natural local metric; ordered discrete variables carry an order but no meaningful spacing; categorical variables carry neither order nor metric, only identity. A direct-search method needs a notion of neighborhood in order to poll, and on a heterogeneous decision space there is no single neighborhood structure appropriate for all three kinds of variables at once. Applying direct search after imposing artificial distances, arbitrary categorical orderings, or numerical spacings on finite-valued variables makes the algorithm operate on a geometry introduced by the modeler rather than on the structure of the problem.

Such heterogeneous black-box decision problems arise naturally in computational operations research and simulation-based engineering, where decisions may combine continuous design parameters, ordered technological choices, and nominal configuration variables, while objective values are obtained from computational simulation models.

A second, seemingly unrelated, difficulty appears even when all variables are continuous. When the variable ranges differ by several orders of magnitude, a step interpreted in physical units explores some coordinates too coarsely and others too finely; the search geometry is then distorted by the units of the problem rather than by its objectives. Scale heterogeneity and mixed-variable heterogeneity are usually treated as separate difficulties. In the present framework they share a structural source: the identification of the space in which the search geometry is defined with the space in which the objective is evaluated.

The central idea of this paper is to separate these two roles. All polling operations are carried out in a *canonical search space*, where each variable is represented in an intrinsic form—a normalized coordinate for a continuous variable, an integer index for an ordered discrete variable, an identity index for a categorical variable. Objective values are computed only in the original *decision space*, reached through a reconstruction operator; the objective is never evaluated in the canonical space. A single step-size parameter governs the search in all three blocks, with one common interpretation as the fraction of the variable domain explored at the current iteration. Because the canonical representation discards the physical units, the numerical spacing, and the labels of the variables, the search geometry no longer depends on them: affine rescaling of continuous variables, order-preserving relabeling of ordered discrete variables, and arbitrary relabeling of categorical variables leave the canonical trajectory unchanged. The method does not place all variable types into a common metric space; each block is polled in its own native geometry, while Pareto dominance is used only in the objective space.

The resulting method, denoted DMS-SI-Mix, is a deterministic direct multisearch framework for mixed-variable multiobjective derivative-free optimization. It keeps the DMS mechanism—a nondominated list, poll centers selected from the list, success measured by list updates—and replaces continuous polling by a *mixed poll* that combines three intrinsic neighborhood operators: normalized direct-search moves on the continuous block, rank moves on the ordered discrete block, and rank moves under a deterministic neighborhood rotation on the categorical block. The categorical mechanism provides locality without imposing a permanent ordering on the categories.

The contributions of this paper are fivefold.

- (i) A direct-search framework for multiobjective derivative-free optimization over heterogeneous decision spaces, built on a strict separation between a canonical search space and the real evaluation space, with continuous, ordered discrete, and categorical variables treated together and without a global metric on the decision space.
- (ii) A representation-invariance property: under affine rescaling of continuous variables, order-preserving relabeling of ordered discrete variables, and arbitrary relabeling of categorical variables, the canonical search trajectory is unchanged (Theorem 3.6).
- (iii) A single resolution parameter governing the search across all variable types, instantiated block by block as a geometric step, a discrete rank move, and a categorical rank move under a deterministic permutation schedule

that exposes categorical alternatives without a fixed metric or embedding on the categorical set.

- (iv) A modular convergence analysis: along refining subsequences, accumulation points are mixed-block Pareto stationary (Theorem 4.7), combining Pareto–Clarke stationarity along the continuous polling directions with weak local Pareto optimality on the ordered discrete and categorical blocks.
- (v) A reproducible computational study on continuous benchmarks under controlled scale heterogeneity, on an engineering piezo-shunt design problem, and on mixed-variable benchmark pairs; the benchmark construction and the deterministic reproducibility of the runs are by-products of independent interest for computational optimization.

The scope of the convergence result is deliberately conservative: the analysis is local, blockwise, and conditional on the existence of a refining subsequence, and does not claim full Pareto–Clarke criticality on the heterogeneous space or global optimality.

Direct Multisearch [1] provides a deterministic derivative-free framework for multiobjective optimization in continuous spaces; DMulti-MADS [3] extends MADS to nonaggregated multiobjective optimization, also for continuous variables. Derivative-free methods for mixed and categorical variables have been developed mainly in the single-objective setting: mixed-variable MADS [4, 5] handles categorical variables through user-supplied neighborhoods, CatMADS [6] through problem-specific learned distances, and CatCMA with Margin [7] through a joint Gaussian–categorical distribution; surrogate-based approaches use learned embeddings of the categorical domain [8]. Surrogate methods for computationally expensive mixed-integer black-box problems, such as SO-MI [9], address a single-objective, stochastic global setting over continuous and integer variables, without a nominal categorical block. General accounts of derivative-free and direct-search optimization are given in [10, 11, 12]. A recurring feature of these methods is a metric, embedding, or learned-distance construction on the categorical block, and most of them address one axis of heterogeneity at a time: multiple objectives in continuous spaces, or mixed variables in single-objective problems. To the author’s knowledge, DMS-SI-Mix is the first deterministic direct-search method that treats multiple objectives together with continuous, ordered discrete, and categorical variables, avoids an embedding or metric on the categorical domain, and is supported by a convergence analysis in the intrinsic geometry of each block. The scale-invariant separation principle is developed for the continuous single-objective setting in a companion paper [13] and for the single-objective mixed-variable setting in [14]; a deterministic categorical neighborhood mechanism for the single-objective case appears in the preprint [15], and a metric-space view of mixed-variable domains in the companion work [16].

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents DMS-SI-Mix: the canonical search space, the reconstruction operator, the nondominated list, and the algorithm. Section 3 develops the intrinsic neighborhood operators for the three variable types. Section 4 states the convergence certificate. Section 5 reports the computational study. Sections 6 and 7 discuss the results and conclude. Technical details—benchmark construction, the categorical permutation schedules, the convergence proofs, and implementation—are collected in the appendices.

2. Direct Multisearch over Canonical Mixed Spaces

This section defines DMS-SI-Mix as an algorithm: the heterogeneous decision space, the canonical representation on which the search operates, the reconstruction operator, the nondominated list, the cache, and the direct multisearch iteration. The intrinsic poll operators for the continuous, ordered discrete, and categorical blocks are deferred to Section 3 and used here only through their common interface. The representation-invariance property is stated in Section 3, after the block poll operators have been defined.

2.1. Heterogeneous decision space and canonical representation

We consider the bound-constrained multiobjective problem

$$\min_{x \in \Omega} F(x) = (f_1(x), \dots, f_q(x)), \quad F : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^q, \quad q \geq 2, \quad (1)$$

whose decision space has a product structure over three native variable types.

Definition 2.1 (Heterogeneous decision space). Let $\{1, \dots, n\}$ be partitioned into three disjoint index sets $\mathcal{I}_C, \mathcal{I}_D, \mathcal{I}_K$, corresponding to *continuous*, *ordered discrete*, and *categorical* variables, with cardinalities n_C, n_D, n_K . The decision space is $\Omega = \Omega_C \times \Omega_D \times \Omega_K$, where

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega_C &= \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}_C} [\ell_i, u_i], & \ell_i < u_i, \\ \Omega_D &= \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}_D} V_i, & V_i = \{v_{i,1} < v_{i,2} < \dots < v_{i,N_i}\}, \quad N_i \geq 2, \\ \Omega_K &= \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}_K} K_i, & K_i = \{c_{i,1}, c_{i,2}, \dots, c_{i,m_i}\}, \quad m_i \geq 2.\end{aligned}$$

The continuous block carries the Euclidean geometry of each interval, the ordered discrete block carries the integer order of each V_i , and the categorical block carries identity only: no order or metric is assumed on the elements of K_i .

Definition 2.2 (Pareto dominance). For $x, x' \in \Omega$, we write $x < x'$ and say that x *Pareto-dominates* x' if $f_\ell(x) \leq f_\ell(x')$ for all $\ell = 1, \dots, q$, with strict inequality for at least one objective component.

Pareto dominance is used only in the objective space \mathbb{R}^q . No metric, scalarization, or embedding on the heterogeneous decision space is needed to decide whether one evaluated point dominates another.

The search, however, does not operate on Ω directly. To each point we associate a *canonical state* in which every block is represented in an intrinsic, dimensionless form.

Definition 2.3 (Canonical space and canonical state). The *canonical space* is

$$\Xi := [0, 1]^{n_C} \times \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}_D} \{1, \dots, N_i\} \times \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}_K} \{1, \dots, m_i\}. \quad (2)$$

A *canonical state* is a triple $\xi = (y, \mathbf{k}, h) \in \Xi$, where $y = (y_i)_{i \in \mathcal{I}_C}$ collects normalized continuous coordinates, $\mathbf{k} = (k_i)_{i \in \mathcal{I}_D}$ collects ordered discrete indices, and $h = (h_i)_{i \in \mathcal{I}_K}$ collects categorical *identity* indices: $h_i = j$ means the variable holds the category $c_{i,j}$, not a position in any ordering of K_i .

Definition 2.4 (Reconstruction operator). The *reconstruction operator* $\Psi : \Xi \rightarrow \Omega$ maps canonical states to real decision vectors componentwise by

$$\Psi(\xi)_i = \begin{cases} \ell_i + (u_i - \ell_i)y_i, & i \in \mathcal{I}_C, \\ v_{i,k_i}, & i \in \mathcal{I}_D, \\ c_{i,h_i}, & i \in \mathcal{I}_K. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Lemma 2.5 (Bijectivity of the reconstruction). *The reconstruction operator $\Psi : \Xi \rightarrow \Omega$ is a bijection.*

Proof. For each continuous coordinate, $y_i \mapsto \ell_i + (u_i - \ell_i)y_i$ is a bijection between $[0, 1]$ and $[\ell_i, u_i]$. For each ordered discrete or categorical coordinate, reconstruction is an index-to-value lookup between two finite sets of the same cardinality. The product of these componentwise bijections is a bijection from Ξ to Ω . \square

The framework keeps three roles structurally separate. The canonical state ξ is the *internal identity* of a point: equality of trial points, cache lookup, and list membership are all expressed in canonical coordinates. The *neighborhood operator* defines locality and is type dependent—a geometric move on the continuous block, a rank move on each finite block (Section 3). *Objective evaluation* takes place only after reconstruction: a trial state ξ' is decoded to $x' = \Psi(\xi')$, and the black box returns $F(x')$; the black box is never asked to evaluate a canonical state. For analysis it is convenient to write the pullback $\tilde{F} := F \circ \Psi : \Xi \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^q$, but this notation does not change where evaluations occur—the problem is posed on Ω , and every objective value used by the algorithm is computed as $F(\Psi(\xi))$ in physical units.

This separation between the search representation and the evaluation space is the structural device of the method, and the mechanism behind its scale-invariant behavior. Affine rescaling of a continuous variable, order-preserving relabeling of an ordered discrete domain, and arbitrary relabeling of a categorical domain all change Ω and the reconstruction Ψ , but leave the canonical space Ξ and the operations performed on it unchanged. The search is governed by a single resolution parameter α , common to all variable types, with initial value $\alpha_0 \in (0, 1]$ and one common interpretation as the fraction of the native domain explored at the current iteration; its block-specific instantiation is given in Section 3, and a single decrease of α refines all three blocks at once.

2.2. Nondominated list and the direct multisearch iteration

DMS-SI-Mix keeps the Direct Multisearch mechanism: it maintains a list of nondominated points rather than a single iterate, polls around a point selected from the list, and measures success by changes to the list.

Nondominated list. At iteration t the algorithm maintains a finite list

$$\mathcal{L}_t = \{(\xi_j, \alpha_j, F_j)\}_{j \in J_t}, \quad \xi_j \in \Xi, \alpha_j > 0, F_j = F(\Psi(\xi_j)) \in \mathbb{R}^q,$$

such that no F_j Pareto-dominates another, the canonical states ξ_j are pairwise distinct, and each entry carries its own resolution parameter α_j . The list is the object returned to the user and the set from which iterates are drawn.

Poll center selection. At each iteration a list entry (ξ_j, α_j, F_j) is selected as *poll center*; the pair (ξ_j, α_j) determines the trial points generated. The selection rule is deterministic. A round-robin rule is the default theoretical choice, since it guarantees that every persistent entry is selected infinitely often; other deterministic orderings, such as spread-based orderings, may be used in computations. The convergence analysis depends only on the resulting fairness property (Section 4), not on a particular rule.

Mixed poll. Given a poll center (ξ_j, α_j) , a finite set of trial canonical states $\mathcal{P}(\xi_j, \alpha_j) \subset \Xi$, the *mixed poll set*, is generated. Each trial differs from ξ_j in exactly one native block: a continuous move in normalized coordinates, an ordered discrete rank move, or a categorical rank move under a deterministic rotating neighborhood. The construction of these operators is the subject of Section 3; for the algorithmic description, \mathcal{P} is used only as an operator that returns canonical trial states.

Cache. Evaluations are cached to avoid recomputation when F is expensive.

Definition 2.6 (Canonical cache entry). A *cache entry* is a triple $(\xi, x, F(x))$ with $\xi \in \Xi$, $x = \Psi(\xi) \in \Omega$, and $F(x) \in \mathbb{R}^q$. The cache C is a collection of such entries indexed by canonical states.

Given a trial state ξ' , the algorithm first checks C : if ξ' is already present, the stored value is reused; otherwise $x' = \Psi(\xi')$ is evaluated and the new entry appended. Because the cache is keyed by the canonical state—and, in the categorical block, by identities rather than positions in any permutation—it remains valid under the rotation mechanism of Section 3. In the theoretical description, cache matching is exact; in implementations the finite indices are matched exactly while continuous coordinates are matched within a small tolerance for floating-point robustness. This tolerance is an implementation device; the convergence analysis uses exact canonical matching.

Acceptance and success.

Definition 2.7 (Acceptable trial; successful and complete polls). A trial ξ' is *acceptable* if no current list entry Pareto-dominates it, that is, $F_j \not\prec F(\Psi(\xi'))$ for every $(\xi_j, \alpha_j, F_j) \in \mathcal{L}_t$. Let \mathcal{L}_t^+ be the list obtained after all trials of iteration t have been processed—acceptable trials inserted, dominated entries removed, so that \mathcal{L}_t^+ is again nondominated. The iteration is *successful* if $\mathcal{L}_t^+ \neq \mathcal{L}_t$ and *unsuccessful* otherwise. New accepted trials enter the list with the poll step size used to generate them. If a dominating accepted trial removes the poll center from the list, no step-size update is applied to that removed entry. Every poll is *complete*: all trials of $\mathcal{P}(\xi_j, \alpha_j)$ are processed before the iteration is declared successful or unsuccessful; opportunistic variants, which stop after the first accepted trial, are not part of the convergence analysis of this paper.

Step-size update. After a complete poll of entry j , its resolution parameter is updated by the standard Direct Multisearch rule

$$\alpha_j^+ = \begin{cases} \gamma \alpha_j, & \mathcal{L}_t^+ \neq \mathcal{L}_t \quad (\text{successful}), \\ \beta \alpha_j, & \mathcal{L}_t^+ = \mathcal{L}_t \quad (\text{unsuccessful}), \end{cases} \quad \beta \in (0, 1), \quad \gamma \geq 1. \quad (4)$$

A successful iteration keeps or expands the step size; an unsuccessful one contracts it. The same update is applied regardless of which variable type produced a successful trial. The conservative choice $\gamma = 1$ is the variant covered by the convergence certificate of Section 4; the success-expansion choice $\gamma > 1$ is the accelerated variant used in the numerical experiments, and the paper does not claim that the certificate for $\gamma = 1$ extends automatically to the unconditional success-expansion regime.

Algorithm 1 DMS-SI-Mix

```
1: Choose an initial canonical state  $\xi_0 \in \Xi$  and  $\alpha_0 \in (0, 1]$ ; fix  $\beta \in (0, 1)$ ,  $\gamma \geq 1$ 
2: Evaluate  $F(\Psi(\xi_0))$ ; initialize  $\mathcal{L}_0 = \{(\xi_0, \alpha_0, F(\Psi(\xi_0)))\}$  and the cache  $C$ 
3: for  $t = 0, 1, 2, \dots$  do
4:   Select a poll center  $(\xi_j, \alpha_j, F_j)$  from  $\mathcal{L}_t$ 
5:   Generate the complete mixed poll set  $\mathcal{P}(\xi_j, \alpha_j)$  ▷ Section 3
6:   for all  $\xi' \in \mathcal{P}(\xi_j, \alpha_j)$  do
7:     if  $\xi'$  is found in the cache  $C$  then
8:       retrieve the stored value  $F(\Psi(\xi'))$ 
9:     else
10:      evaluate  $F(\Psi(\xi'))$  and append the new cache entry
11:    end if
12:  end for
13:  Form  $\mathcal{L}_t^+$ : insert acceptable trials with the poll step size, remove dominated entries
14:  if the poll of  $j$  was unsuccessful then
15:    Advance the categorical rotation counters of entry  $j$  ▷ Section 3; before the step-size update
16:  end if
17:  Update  $\alpha_j$  by (4); the remaining list-entry parameters are unchanged
18:  if a stopping criterion is satisfied then
19:    return  $\mathcal{L}_t^+$ 
20:  end if
21:   $\mathcal{L}_{t+1} \leftarrow \mathcal{L}_t^+$ 
22: end for
```

2.3. The DMS-SI-Mix algorithm

The objects above assemble into Algorithm 1. The algorithm has no search step; all trial points are generated by the mixed poll; its overall structure is summarized in Figure 1. It is fully deterministic: for a fixed list-ordering rule and fixed permutation schedules, a run is reproducible without averaging.

Typical stopping criteria are a maximum number of black-box evaluations, all active resolution parameters below a prescribed threshold, or stagnation of the nondominated list over a prescribed number of iterations. Implementation details—the matching tolerance, the data structure for C , and the initialization of \mathcal{L}_0 —are collected in Appendix D.

DMS-SI-Mix is a direct multisearch method: it keeps a nondominated list, selects poll centers from it, filters evaluated trials by Pareto dominance, and attaches a step-size parameter to each list entry. Its mixed-variable character comes from the canonical state, the reconstruction operator, and the mixed poll set. When \mathcal{I}_D and \mathcal{I}_K are empty the canonical space reduces to $[0, 1]^{n_c}$, the mixed poll becomes an ordinary continuous poll, and the method differs from standard DMS only in that polling is performed in normalized rather than physical coordinates. The next section defines the three intrinsic poll operators and establishes the representation-invariance property that justifies the scale-invariant terminology.

3. Intrinsic Polling by Variable Type

Section 2 treated the mixed poll set $\mathcal{P}(\xi, \alpha)$ as an abstract operator. This section constructs it. Each block contributes a neighborhood operator derived from its native structure—Euclidean geometry for the continuous block, integer order for the ordered discrete block, unordered identity for the categorical block—and the single resolution parameter α is given a block-specific instantiation as the fraction of the native domain explored. The three operators are assembled into \mathcal{P} , illustrated on a small example, and shown to make the canonical trajectory invariant under representation changes.

3.1. Continuous and ordered discrete poll moves

Continuous block. For $i \in \mathcal{I}_C$, the canonical coordinate is the normalized scalar $y_i \in [0, 1]$, related to the physical coordinate by $y_i = (x_i - \ell_i)/(u_i - \ell_i)$. Polling is geometric in these coordinates.

Figure 1: Conceptual structure of one iteration of DMS-SI-Mix. A poll center (ξ, α_j) is selected from the nondominated list \mathcal{L}_t by round-robin rotation. The mixed poll set $\mathcal{P}(\xi, \alpha_j)$ is generated by three variable-type-specific neighborhood operators—continuous, discrete, and categorical (CC-DNR)—all governed by the single resolution parameter α_j , and all acting in the canonical state space Ξ . Trial points are decoded by Ψ to the original space Ω and evaluated; the list is updated by Pareto dominance; and α_j is expanded by γ on successful iterations and contracted by β on unsuccessful ones. The active CC-DNR permutation $\pi_i^{(\rho_{i,j} \bmod P_i)}$ is indexed by the rank-one rotation counter $\rho_{i,j}$ of the selected poll center. The figure is a conceptual overview; precise definitions are given in Sections 2–3.

Definition 3.1 (Continuous neighborhood). Let $\mathcal{D}_C \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_C}$ be a finite positive spanning set. For $y^\star \in [0, 1]^{n_C}$ and $\alpha > 0$,

$$N^C(y^\star; \alpha) := \{ \text{proj}_{[0,1]^{n_C}}(y^\star + \alpha d) : d \in \mathcal{D}_C \},$$

where $\text{proj}_{[0,1]^{n_C}}$ is the Euclidean projection onto the unit hypercube. Trials coinciding with y^\star , which occur only when projection saturates a boundary, are discarded. The canonical choice $\mathcal{D}_C = \{\pm e_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}_C}$ recovers one-coordinate-at-a-time polling, with $|N^C(y^\star; \alpha)| \leq 2n_C$.

A move of magnitude α in the canonical coordinate y_i corresponds, through Ψ , to a physical move of magnitude $\alpha(u_i - \ell_i)$ in x_i . The relative step α is therefore independent of the physical scale of $[\ell_i, u_i]$.

Projection, canonicalization, and barrier treatment. The projection in Definition 3.1 reflects the *canonicalization* performed by the implementation. After a poll displacement is generated, the trial point is mapped back to the canonical mixed space Ξ : for continuous variables this amounts to clipping the trial coordinate to $[0, 1]$; for ordered discrete and categorical variables, canonicalization enforces membership in the corresponding finite canonical grids (see Section 3). Canonicalization should not be confused with the *barrier* treatment of general constraints. Canonical box bounds are enforced by canonicalization; additional problem constraints, when present, are handled by an extreme-barrier convention, following the multiobjective treatment of the original DMS framework [1] and in the standard spirit of constrained direct-search methods [17, Sec. 13.1]: a trial point that violates such a constraint is rejected and F is not evaluated. At interior continuous points and for sufficiently small α , the projection is inactive and the canonical poll coincides with the unprojected displacement $y^\star + \alpha d$; this property is used in the proof of Proposition 4.3. Near the canonical boundary, projection may shorten a displacement or make the projected trial coincide with the poll center; such degenerate trials are discarded.

Ordered discrete block. For $i \in \mathcal{I}_D$, the canonical coordinate is the integer index $k_i \in \{1, \dots, N_i\}$ into the ordered set $V_i = \{v_{i,1} < \dots < v_{i,N_i}\}$. The numerical values $v_{i,j}$ carry no algorithmic role; only the order does. The natural size of the block is not the range of values but the number of elementary jumps between the extreme indices, the *combinatorial diameter* $N_i - 1$.

Definition 3.2 (Discrete rank and neighborhood). For $i \in \mathcal{I}_D$ and $\alpha > 0$, the *discrete rank* is

$$r_i^D(\alpha) := \max\{1, \text{round}(\alpha(N_i - 1))\}. \quad (5)$$

For $k_i^\star \in \{1, \dots, N_i\}$, the *discrete neighborhood* is

$$N_i^D(k_i^\star; \alpha) := \{ \text{clamp}(k_i^\star + \delta, 1, N_i) : \delta \in \{+r_i^D(\alpha), -r_i^D(\alpha)\} \},$$

with $\text{clamp}(a, 1, N_i) := \max\{1, \min\{N_i, a\}\}$. Trivial trials, where clamping returns k_i^\star , are discarded.

At $\alpha = 1$ the rank is $r_i^D = N_i - 1$, a full traversal between the extreme indices—the discrete analogue of the full-range continuous step; rank-one moves (adjacent indices) are reached for $\alpha < 3/(2(N_i - 1))$. Both the rank and the clamp depend on V_i only through the indices, not through the values $v_{i,j}$, so the discrete poll is unchanged under any order-preserving relabeling of V_i . Integer variables and granular variables with non-uniform spacing are covered without modification: only the order of V_i enters.

3.2. Categorical poll moves and deterministic rotation

For $i \in \mathcal{I}_K$, the domain $K_i = \{c_{i,1}, \dots, c_{i,m_i}\}$ carries neither order nor metric; the canonical coordinate h_i records which identity is held, not a position. Defining a neighborhood therefore raises a structural question: with no order and no metric, no pair of categories is a priori closer than any other. Locality must be *constructed* algorithmically.

The construction is the *deterministic neighborhood rotation* (DNR) mechanism. For each $i \in \mathcal{I}_K$ it maintains a deterministic family of permutations $\pi_i^{(e)} \in S_{m_i}$, indexed by an integer rotation index e . A fixed permutation π turns K_i into a cycle, on which rank-based moves are defined as in the discrete block, with one difference: a cycle has no extreme indices, so ranks beyond the half-cycle produce no new neighbors.

Definition 3.3 (Categorical rank and neighborhood at a fixed permutation). For $i \in \mathcal{I}_K$ and $\alpha > 0$, the *categorical rank* is

$$r_i^K(\alpha) := \min\{\lfloor m_i/2 \rfloor, \max\{1, \text{round}(\alpha m_i)\}\}. \quad (6)$$

Let $\pi \in S_{m_i}$ be the permutation active at the current poll, and let $j^* := \pi^{-1}(h_i^*)$ be the cyclic position of the identity h_i^* under π . The *categorical neighborhood* is

$$N_i^K(h_i^*; \alpha) := \{\pi(j') : j' \equiv j^* \pm r_i^K(\alpha) \pmod{m_i}, j' \in \{1, \dots, m_i\}\}.$$

The operator returns identities: it acts on h_i^* and produces canonical identities, with π entering only through the cyclic adjacency it defines on positions.

The rank is saturated at $\lfloor m_i/2 \rfloor$, the maximal nonredundant cyclic separation; at $\alpha = 1$ it equals $\lfloor m_i/2 \rfloor$, and rank-one moves are reached for $\alpha < 3/(2m_i)$.

Center-local rotation. The active permutation is not advanced on a global clock. Each list entry j carries, for each categorical coordinate i , an integer *rotation counter* $\rho_{i,j} \in \mathbb{N}_0$, initialized at zero. When entry j is polled, the active permutation for block i is $\pi_i^{(\rho_{i,j} \bmod P_i)}$. The counter advances by one after a complete unsuccessful poll of entry j whose poll step size lies in the rank-one regime of block i , that is, $\bar{\alpha}_j < 3/(2m_i)$; successful polls leave it unchanged. The counter is thus center-local: the permutation an entry sees depends only on its own rank-one-regime unsuccessful polls, not on a global iteration count. The schedule $\pi_i^{(e)}$ is deterministic and is constructed so that, over one period P_i , every pair of categories is exposed as rank-one neighbors; the construction (covering cycles, after Walecki) and its coverage property are given in [Appendix B](#). Crucially, rotation changes only the neighborhood operator: the canonical identity h_i is a coordinate of ξ and is untouched, which is what keeps the cache of [Section 2](#) consistent under rotation.

3.3. The mixed poll set

The three block operators of [Sections 3.1](#) and [3.2](#) share a common interface: each takes a canonical state and a resolution α and returns canonical trial states.

Definition 3.4 (Mixed poll set). Writing $\mathcal{P}_C(\xi, \alpha)$, $\mathcal{P}_D(\xi, \alpha)$, $\mathcal{P}_K(\xi, \alpha)$ for the sets of trials obtained by applying, respectively, the continuous neighborhood N^C to the continuous block, the discrete neighborhood N_i^D to each $i \in \mathcal{I}_D$, and the categorical neighborhood N_i^K to each $i \in \mathcal{I}_K$, the *mixed poll set* at $\xi = (y, \mathbf{k}, h)$ and $\alpha > 0$ is their union,

$$\mathcal{P}(\xi, \alpha) = \mathcal{P}_C(\xi, \alpha) \cup \mathcal{P}_D(\xi, \alpha) \cup \mathcal{P}_K(\xi, \alpha).$$

Each element of $\mathcal{P}(\xi, \alpha)$ differs from ξ in exactly one native coordinate: either one continuous coordinate is displaced in normalized space, one ordered discrete rank is changed with all other ranks fixed, or one categorical identity is replaced by a neighbor under the active permutation with all other identities fixed. For instance, an ordered discrete trial has the form

$$(y, \mathbf{k}', h), \quad k'_i \neq k_i, \quad k'_\ell = k_\ell \quad (\ell \neq i),$$

and the analogous one-coordinate convention applies in the continuous and categorical blocks.

The number of trials is at most $|\mathcal{D}_C| + 2n_D + 2n_K$, typically fewer because of boundary trivialities in the continuous and discrete blocks. A single decrease of α refines all three blocks at once: once α is below $\min\{3/(2(N_i - 1)), 3/(2m_i)\}$ over all finite blocks, every finite rank equals one, while the continuous step magnitude in canonical coordinates equals α and tends to zero. The poll is separable in the decision variables, but acceptance is multiobjective and global: after reconstruction and evaluation, every trial is compared with the current nondominated list in objective space.

Example 3.5 (A mixed poll). Consider three variables, one of each type:

$$x_1 \in [0, 10], \quad x_2 \in \{1, 2, \dots, 11\}, \quad x_3 \in \{c_1, \dots, c_5\},$$

with canonical state $\xi = (0.4, 6, 3)$, which reconstructs to $x_1 = 4, x_2 = 6, x_3 = c_3$. Take $\alpha = 0.6$ and $\mathcal{D}_C = \{+1, -1\}$.

Continuous. The canonical move is $y_1 \pm \alpha = 0.4 \pm 0.6$, projected onto $[0, 1]$ to give $\{0, 1\}$; real-space trials $x_1 \in \{0, 10\}$.

Discrete. The combinatorial diameter is $N_2 - 1 = 10$, so $r_2^D(0.6) = \max\{1, \text{round}(6)\} = 6$. Index trials $k_2 \pm 6 = \{0, 12\}$, clamped into $\{1, \dots, 11\}$ to give $\{1, 11\}$; real-space trials $x_2 \in \{1, 11\}$.

Categorical. Here $m_3 = 5$, so $r_3^K(0.6) = \min\{2, \max\{1, \text{round}(3)\}\} = \min\{2, 3\} = 2$: the half-cycle cap is active. With active permutation $\pi = (3, 1, 4, 2, 5)$, the identity $h_3 = 3$ sits at position $j^* = \pi^{-1}(3) = 1$; the rank-two cyclic positions $j^* \pm 2 \pmod{5}$ are $\{3, 4\}$, with identities $\pi(\{3, 4\}) = \{4, 2\}$; real-space trials $x_3 \in \{c_4, c_2\}$.

Collecting the three blocks, the mixed poll set is

$$P(\xi, 0.6) = \{(0, 6, 3), (1, 6, 3), (0.4, 1, 3), (0.4, 11, 3), (0.4, 6, 4), (0.4, 6, 2)\} \subset \Xi,$$

which reconstructs in the decision space to

$$\{(0, 6, c_3), (10, 6, c_3), (4, 1, c_3), (4, 11, c_3), (4, 6, c_4), (4, 6, c_2)\};$$

six trials, two from each block, each differing from ξ in exactly one canonical coordinate.

3.4. Representation invariance

The block operators of Sections 3.1 and 3.2 act on canonical coordinates only: the continuous neighborhood on $y \in [0, 1]^{n_c}$, the discrete neighborhood on indices k_i , the categorical neighborhood on identities h_i . None of them reads the physical bounds $[\ell_i, u_i]$, the discrete values $v_{i,j}$, or the category labels $c_{i,j}$. This is the structural reason for the following invariance.

Theorem 3.6 (Representation invariance of the canonical trajectory). *Let $T : \Omega \rightarrow \Omega'$ be any composition of representation changes of the following kinds: (a) componentwise affine rescaling of continuous variables, $x_i \mapsto a_i x_i + b_i$ with $a_i > 0$ for $i \in \mathcal{I}_C$; (b) order-preserving relabeling of an ordered discrete domain V_i , $i \in \mathcal{I}_D$; (c) arbitrary relabeling of a categorical domain K_i , $i \in \mathcal{I}_K$. Let $F' := F \circ T^{-1}$ be the objective of the transformed problem, with reconstruction operator Ψ' . Then $\Psi' = T \circ \Psi$, and under identical initialization in canonical coordinates, identical parameters $(\alpha_0, \beta, \gamma)$, identical permutation schedules, and exact arithmetic, Algorithm 1 applied to F and to F' produces identical sequences of canonical states and identical nondominated lists,*

$$\xi'_t = \xi_t, \quad \mathcal{L}'_t = \mathcal{L}_t \quad \text{for all } t \geq 0,$$

while the real iterates are related by $x'_t = \Psi'(\xi'_t) = T(x_t)$.

Proof sketch. Each change (a)–(c) renames the real domain without altering the canonical space Ξ : under (a) the i -th continuous component of Ψ' is $y_i \mapsto a_i(\ell_i + (u_i - \ell_i)y_i) + b_i$, exactly T composed with the i -th component of Ψ ; under (b) and (c) the index-to-value lookups are replaced while the indices k_i, h_i themselves are unchanged. Hence $\Psi' = T \circ \Psi$. The equality $\xi'_t = \xi_t$ then follows by induction on t : identical canonical initialization gives the base case, and at each iteration both runs select the same poll center, generate the same mixed poll set—the block operators read only canonical coordinates—and, since $F'(\Psi'(\xi)) = F(T^{-1}(T(\Psi(\xi)))) = F(\Psi(\xi))$, assign the same objective vector to every trial. All Pareto comparisons, list updates, and step-size and rotation-counter updates therefore coincide, so $\mathcal{L}'_{t+1} = \mathcal{L}_{t+1}$. Applying $\Psi' = T \circ \Psi$ to the common canonical state gives $x'_t = T(x_t)$. The full argument is given in Appendix C. \square

Theorem 3.6 is a pointwise, finite-trajectory statement, holding at every iteration: the *canonical* trajectory is literally identical across representations, while the real iterates are equivariant, $x'_t = T(x_t)$, transforming exactly as the representation map prescribes. The physical iterates are not claimed to be equal. Affine rescaling, order-preserving discrete relabeling, and categorical relabeling are precisely the transformations that carry no algorithmic information, in the sense that they leave the canonical space and the intrinsic operators unchanged; the search geometry is driven entirely by the canonical state, and this is what justifies the scale-invariant terminology of DMS-SI-Mix.

4. A Minimal Convergence Certificate

This section establishes a conservative convergence certificate for DMS-SI-Mix. The certificate is conditional and modular: under suitable assumptions, *if* the algorithm generates a refining subsequence—a frozen-finite-block subsequence along which the step size vanishes—*then* any accumulation point of the canonical iterates is mixed-block Pareto stationary, in a sense made precise below. The result asserts nothing about the unconditional existence of such a subsequence, and the stationarity it certifies on the finite blocks is weak rather than full local Pareto optimality. The full proofs of the three block-level results and of the assembled theorem are deferred to [Appendix C](#).

4.1. Standing assumptions and refining subsequences

We use the following standing assumptions on the problem and the algorithm.

- (A1) *Finiteness of blocks and objectives.* The index sets $\mathcal{I}_C, \mathcal{I}_D, \mathcal{I}_K$ are finite; for each $i \in \mathcal{I}_D$, $2 \leq N_i < \infty$; for each $i \in \mathcal{I}_K$, $2 \leq m_i < \infty$; and the number of objectives q is finite.
- (A2) *Regularity on continuous fibers.* For every fixed pair (\mathbf{k}^*, h^*) and every objective component $\ell \in \{1, \dots, q\}$, the fiber objective $(F_{\mathbf{k}^*, h^*})_\ell : [0, 1]^{n_c} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, obtained by freezing the finite blocks and reading the continuous block in canonical coordinates, is locally Lipschitz continuous.
- (A3) *Fixed positive-spanning continuous directions.* There exists a finite set $\mathcal{D}_C \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_c}$ that positively spans \mathbb{R}^{n_c} and is used as the continuous polling set at every iteration.
- (A4) *Non-expansive step-size rule.* The step-size update (4) is performed with $\gamma = 1$: successful iterations leave the step size unchanged, and unsuccessful iterations multiply it by a fixed $\beta \in (0, 1)$. The step size of every list entry is therefore monotone non-increasing.
- (A5) *Fair poll-center selection.* The selection rule of Section 2.2 is *fair*: every list entry that persists in the nondominated list is selected as poll center infinitely often.

These five assumptions are imposed throughout this section. We comment briefly on (A4), which is more restrictive than the operational rule of Section 2.2: the operational variant allows expansion ($\gamma > 1$) on successful iterations, while the certificate below is established only for the non-expansive case $\gamma = 1$. This is the conservative choice and aligns with the classical analysis of derivative-free methods, in which monotonicity of the step size along persistent entries is the lever that drives accumulation arguments. The expansion regime is the practical accelerator used in the numerical experiments of Section 5; extending the certificate to it in the present mixed-variable setting is left for future work.

The next assumption is *not* a standing assumption of the method. It is the conditional hypothesis under which the convergence certificate is stated.

Assumption 4.1 (Refining subsequence). *A run of Algorithm 1 generates a refining subsequence if there exist integer index vectors $\mathbf{k}^* \in \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}_D} \{1, \dots, N_i\}$ and $h^* \in \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}_K} \{1, \dots, m_i\}$, an infinite set of iteration indices $\mathcal{T} \subset \mathbb{N}_0$, and a list entry j^* that remains in the list throughout \mathcal{T} , such that every $t \in \mathcal{T}$ is an unsuccessful poll of j^* with*

$$\alpha_t \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } t \rightarrow \infty, t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (\mathbf{k}^{(t)}, h^{(t)}) = (\mathbf{k}^*, h^*) \text{ for every } t \in \mathcal{T},$$

where $\xi_t = (y_t, \mathbf{k}^{(t)}, h^{(t)})$ is the canonical state of the selected poll center at iteration t , with step size α_t . The pair (\mathbf{k}^*, h^*) is the fiber of the refining subsequence.

The conservative non-expansive rule (A4) keeps the step size monotone non-increasing along any persistent entry, which is what makes $\alpha_t \rightarrow 0$ available along \mathcal{T} . Whether *any* run actually produces such a subsequence is a separate question, addressed in Section 4.3.

4.2. Mixed-block Pareto stationarity

The continuous and finite blocks have different native notions of locality. The continuous block admits Pareto–Clarke stationarity along the fixed polling directions; the finite blocks admit only a weak local Pareto property with respect to their rank-1 or single-coordinate move classes. We formalize the latter, then state each blockwise result separately, and finally assemble them.

Definition 4.2 (Weak local Pareto optimality on a finite move class). Let $\xi^* \in \Xi$, let $x^* := \Psi(\xi^*)$, and let $\mathcal{M}(\xi^*)$ be a finite class of admissible moves, each carrying ξ^* to a canonical neighbor $\xi' \in \Xi$. We say that x^* is *weakly locally Pareto optimal* with respect to $\mathcal{M}(\xi^*)$ if no move in $\mathcal{M}(\xi^*)$ improves every objective component strictly: for every neighbor ξ' reached by a move in $\mathcal{M}(\xi^*)$, there exists $\ell \in \{1, \dots, q\}$ with

$$F_\ell(\Psi(\xi')) \geq F_\ell(x^*).$$

This is strictly weaker than the absence of Pareto domination in the sense of Definition 2.2, which would additionally exclude neighbors that tie x^* in some components and strictly improve it in others.

The three blockwise statements below are established under the standing assumptions; their proofs are given in Appendix C.

Proposition 4.3 (Continuous-fiber Pareto–Clarke stationarity). *Under (A1)–(A5) and Assumption 4.1, let \mathcal{T} be the refining subsequence with fiber (\mathbf{k}^*, h^*) . Any accumulation point y^* of $\{y_t\}_{t \in \mathcal{T}}$ is Pareto–Clarke stationary along \mathcal{D}_C for the fiber objective $F_{\mathbf{k}^*, h^*}$ on $[0, 1]^n$: for every $d \in \mathcal{D}_C$ feasible at y^* , there exists $\ell \in \{1, \dots, q\}$ with $(F_{\mathbf{k}^*, h^*})_\ell^\circ(y^*; d) \geq 0$, where $^\circ$ denotes the Clarke generalized directional derivative [18].*

Proposition 4.4 (Discrete rank-1 weak local Pareto optimality). *Under the same assumptions, the point $x^* := \Psi(y^*, \mathbf{k}^*, h^*)$ is weakly locally Pareto optimal, in the sense of Definition 4.2, with respect to all rank-1 discrete moves: for every $i \in \mathcal{I}_D$ and every $k'_i \in \{k_i^* - 1, k_i^* + 1\} \cap \{1, \dots, N_i\}$, there exists $\ell^* \in \{1, \dots, q\}$ with $F_{\ell^*}(\Psi(\xi^*[k_i \leftarrow k'_i])) \geq F_{\ell^*}(x^*)$.*

Proposition 4.5 (Categorical single-coordinate weak local Pareto optimality). *Under the standing assumptions, Assumption 4.1, and the covering property of the CC-DNR schedule (Appendix B), the point x^* of Proposition 4.4 is weakly locally Pareto optimal, in the sense of Definition 4.2, with respect to all single-coordinate categorical substitutions: for every $i \in \mathcal{I}_K$ and every $h'_i \in \{1, \dots, m_i\}$ with $h'_i \neq h_i^*$, there exists $\ell^* \in \{1, \dots, q\}$ with $F_{\ell^*}(\Psi(\xi^*[h_i \leftarrow h'_i])) \geq F_{\ell^*}(x^*)$.*

The mixed-block stationarity condition is the conjunction of these three blockwise statements.

Definition 4.6 (Mixed-block Pareto stationarity). A canonical state $\xi^* = (y^*, \mathbf{k}^*, h^*) \in \Xi$ is *mixed-block Pareto stationary* for F if it satisfies all of:

- (Si) y^* is Pareto–Clarke stationary along the polling directions \mathcal{D}_C for the fiber objective $F_{\mathbf{k}^*, h^*}$ on $[0, 1]^n$, in the sense of Proposition 4.3;
- (Sii) $x^* := \Psi(\xi^*)$ is weakly locally Pareto optimal with respect to all rank-1 discrete moves, in the sense of Definition 4.2;
- (Siii) x^* is weakly locally Pareto optimal with respect to all single-coordinate categorical substitutions, in the sense of Definition 4.2.

Theorem 4.7 (Conditional mixed-block Pareto stationarity). *Under the standing assumptions (A1)–(A5), if a run of Algorithm 1 generates a refining subsequence in the sense of Assumption 4.1, with index set \mathcal{T} and fiber (\mathbf{k}^*, h^*) , then every accumulation point ξ^* of the canonical iterates $\{\xi_t\}_{t \in \mathcal{T}}$ is mixed-block Pareto stationary in the sense of Definition 4.6; equivalently, $x^* = \Psi(\xi^*)$ satisfies (Si)–(Siii).*

Proof sketch. Along \mathcal{T} the step size satisfies $\alpha_t \rightarrow 0$ and the finite blocks are frozen at (\mathbf{k}^*, h^*) by Assumption 4.1. Compactness of $[0, 1]^n$ yields an accumulation point y^* of $\{y_t\}_{t \in \mathcal{T}}$; set $\xi^* := (y^*, \mathbf{k}^*, h^*)$. Conditions (Si)–(Siii) of Definition 4.6 are then Propositions 4.3, 4.4, and 4.5, respectively. The bijectivity of Ψ (Lemma 2.5) transfers the conclusions to $x^* = \Psi(\xi^*) \in \Omega$. The full proofs of the three block-level results and the auxiliary lemmas they require are given in Appendix C. \square

The structure is modular: each block contributes its own notion of local optimality through its intrinsic neighborhood operator, and no global variational structure is imposed across variable types. The continuous block contributes Pareto–Clarke stationarity along the fixed polling directions; the discrete and categorical blocks contribute weak local Pareto optimality with respect to their intrinsic move classes.

4.3. Scope and limitations

The result is deliberately conservative, in three explicit senses, each of which is a current limitation rather than a hidden assumption.

Conditional on a refining subsequence. Theorem 4.7 assumes the existence of a refining subsequence; it does not assert that such a subsequence is generated unconditionally. Whether a given run produces one depends on the trajectory of the finite blocks and the persistence of list entries, neither of which is controlled by the standing assumptions alone. The certificate characterizes the stationarity properties of accumulation points *along* any refining subsequence the run happens to produce, and is silent otherwise.

Weak, not full, local Pareto optimality on the finite blocks. Conditions (Sii) and (Siii) certify that no admissible rank-1 or single-coordinate move improves every objective component strictly. They do not certify full local Pareto optimality in the sense of Definition 2.2, because rejecting a trial along the refining subsequence certifies only that the trial is no better in *some* component, and this single-component inequality is what survives the passage to the limit. In particular, the certificate does not exclude an accumulation point at which an admissible finite-block move ties the limiting objective vector in every component but one and strictly improves the remaining one. Closing this gap would require a sufficient-decrease margin or a nondegeneracy hypothesis on objective ties, and is left for future work.

Non-expansive step size. The certificate is established for $\gamma = 1$ (Assumption (A4)), which is more restrictive than the success-expansion rule $\gamma > 1$ used in the numerical experiments. Extending the analysis to unconditional success expansion in the present mixed-variable setting is left for future work.

The certificate is therefore minimal in scope: it gives a conditional, modular, blockwise-stationarity statement under conservative assumptions, and isolates exactly the gaps that remain open. We do not claim that DMS-SI-Mix converges to a Pareto–Clarke critical point; we claim that, whenever a refining subsequence exists, accumulation points along it satisfy a mixed-block stationarity condition consistent with the intrinsic geometry of each variable type.

5. Computational Study

This section reports a reproducible computational study in three blocks. The first isolates the continuous component of DMS-SI-Mix on a public suite of 108 multiobjective benchmarks under controlled scale heterogeneity, and supports the claim that normalized polling provides a measurable advantage over standard Direct Multisearch (DMS) when variables span several orders of magnitude. The second is a single engineering instance—a piezoelectric shunt vibration-suppression design with contrast factor $\kappa \approx 1.4 \times 10^7$ —which complements the synthetic benchmarks with an applied test. The third reports results on six benchmark pairs that combine continuous, ordered discrete, and categorical variables, exercising the full mixed poll of Section 3. We report results under the conservative non-expansive regime $\gamma = 1$, covered by Theorem 4.7, and under the accelerated practical regime $\gamma = 2$, which is not covered by that theorem; the two are reported side by side to keep the distinction visible.

All runs are deterministic. The statistical analysis is therefore across problem instances or scaling strategies, not across repeated runs of a stochastic algorithm.

5.1. Setup, metrics, and reproducibility

Budget and determinism. Every run uses an evaluation budget of $N_{\max} = 20\,000$ and is a single deterministic execution. Determinism is inherited from the deterministic CC-DNR schedules and the absence of any stochastic component; no averaging over repeated runs is reported or needed.

Algorithmic parameters. Unless stated otherwise, the scale-invariant runs use $\alpha_0 = 0.1$, corresponding to 10% of each variable domain in canonical coordinates, while the DMS baseline uses its method-native initial step in the original variable space. The cache uses tolerance $\tau = 10^{-8}$ for continuous canonical matching. Two success-expansion configurations are reported in the continuous scale-invariance study: *C1*, with $(\beta, \gamma) = (2/3, 3/2)$, and *C2*, with $(\beta, \gamma) = (1/2, 2)$. Configuration *C2* is the standard operational configuration of public DMS implementations. No hypervolume gate is applied in any run. The default categorical schedule is the covering-cycles construction of [Appendix B](#); rotation is driven by the rank-one counter $\rho_{i,j}$, with no global epoch parameter.

Metrics. Four objective-space metrics are reported, following the methodology of [1]: Hypervolume (HV, primary), Purity, Spread, and Inverted Generational Distance (IGD). Hypervolume uses a pairwise reference-point construction with nadir-plus-margin reference within each comparison, as detailed in [Appendix A.3](#). For mixed-variable problems we additionally report two empirical coverage metrics measured over the *full set of evaluated points* (the cache, not the final nondominated list): *visual categorical coverage* CC_{vis} , the fraction of categorical identities $c \in K_i$, $i \in \mathcal{I}_K$, exercised during the run; and *visual discrete coverage* DC_{vis} , defined analogously over discrete indices. These are exploration diagnostics, not theoretical guarantees: the covering property of [Appendix B](#) certifies that every pair of categories is exposed as rank-one neighbors over one rotation period, but the empirical CC_{vis} , DC_{vis} measured on a finite-budget run is a distinct quantity.

Statistical significance. Across-problem comparisons use one-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with matched-pairs rank-biserial correlation r as effect size. Significance is reported at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, and $p < 0.001$. The Hypervolume reference point is constructed within each scaling strategy; therefore absolute HV values are comparable across the two algorithms within a strategy, but not across strategies. The Wilcoxon statistic and the W/T/L counts (Wins/Ties/Losses for DMS-SI-Mix versus DMS) are the cross-strategy-comparable quantities.

Implementation. All algorithms are implemented in MATLAB. The canonical state is a structured record (y, \mathbf{k}, h) ; reconstruction is a single componentwise function; the cache is keyed by ξ . The continuous benchmark suite and the mixed-variable suite are publicly available [19]; the DMS-SI-Mix implementation will be made available on acceptance and is available to reviewers upon request.

5.2. Scale invariance on continuous benchmarks

To answer the question of whether scale invariance provides a measurable advantage over DMS, we apply both algorithms to 108 continuous multiobjective benchmarks ([Appendix A.1](#)) under eight scaling strategies that induce controlled scale heterogeneity: *baseline* ($\kappa = 1$), *moderate* ($\kappa = 10^4$), *progressive* ($\kappa = 10^6$), *extreme* ($\kappa = 10^8$), *spatial-thermal* ($\kappa \approx 9 \times 10^4$), and three oscillatory variants based on low-discrepancy sequences (*Sobol*, *Sobol-digit*, *Halton*, all at $\kappa = 10^6$). The transformations preserve Pareto-front geometry; the construction is given in [Appendix A.3](#).

The principal cross-strategy comparison is the Wilcoxon test of [Table 1](#), reported under three step-size regimes: the standard DMS configuration *C2* $(\beta, \gamma) = (1/2, 2)$; the alternative operational configuration *C1* $(\beta, \gamma) = (2/3, 3/2)$; and the non-expansive configuration $(\beta, \gamma) = (1/2, 1)$ covered by the convergence analysis of [Section 4](#).

The Wilcoxon analysis exhibits a clear threshold pattern, illustrated for two representative strategies in [Figure 2](#). Under baseline scaling ($\kappa = 1$), the difference between DMS and DMS-SI-Mix is not statistically significant in any of the three regimes (*C2*: $p = 0.85$, $r = -0.12$; *C1*: $p = 0.21$, $r = +0.09$; non-expansive: $p = 0.83$, $r = -0.11$): without scale heterogeneity, the two methods are operationally equivalent. Every heterogeneous strategy, by contrast, yields a highly significant Hypervolume improvement in favor of DMS-SI-Mix ($p < 0.001$ throughout) under all three regimes. The advantage is therefore not a gradual function of κ but a threshold effect: absent under uniform scaling, strong and significant once any genuine heterogeneity is present. Monotone (*moderate*, *progressive*, *extreme*), oscillatory (*Sobol*, *Sobol-digit*, *Halton*), and *spatial-thermal* scalings all exhibit significant positive effects, indicating that the benefit is intrinsic to scale heterogeneity itself, not to a particular reparameterization pattern. The rank-biserial effect size varies with the regime, ranging from moderate ($r \approx 0.42$ – 0.51 in *C1* and the non-expansive regime on monotone strategies) to very strong ($r \approx 0.91$ – 0.96 in the non-expansive regime on *extreme* and the three oscillatory strategies). Effect sizes are compared within a regime, not across regimes, because the Hypervolume reference point is constructed separately within each. Detailed per-strategy profiles $\pi(1.001)$ and $\pi(2)$ for configurations *C1* and *C2* are tabulated in [Appendix A.3](#).

Table 1: Wilcoxon signed-rank test comparing DMS-SI-Mix against DMS on Hypervolume across 108 benchmarks per scaling strategy, under three step-size regimes. One-sided test, H_1 : DMS-SI-Mix > DMS. W is the positive signed-rank sum; r is the matched-pairs rank-biserial correlation; W/T/L are Wins/Ties/Losses for DMS-SI-Mix. Significance: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$. The HV reference point is constructed within each regime, so W/T/L counts and test statistics are comparable within a block but absolute HV values are not comparable across blocks. Full per-strategy HV profiles $\pi(\tau)$ and the corresponding tables for C1 and C2 are reported in [Appendix A.3](#).

Strategy	n	W	p	r	W/T/L	Sig.
<i>C2: standard DMS configuration $(\beta, \gamma) = (1/2, 2)$</i>						
baseline ($\kappa = 1$)	108	2086	8.5×10^{-1}	-0.12	44/11/53	
moderate ($\kappa = 10^4$)	108	4420	1.1×10^{-9}	+0.68	82/6/20	***
progressive ($\kappa = 10^6$)	108	3775	2.4×10^{-5}	+0.47	68/7/33	***
extreme ($\kappa = 10^8$)	108	4033	1.1×10^{-7}	+0.60	71/8/29	***
spatial-thermal ($\kappa \approx 9 \times 10^4$)	108	3573	6.4×10^{-5}	+0.44	65/9/34	***
Sobol oscillatory ($\kappa = 10^6$)	108	4298	1.2×10^{-8}	+0.64	76/6/26	***
Sobol-digit osc. ($\kappa = 10^6$)	108	4198	7.8×10^{-8}	+0.60	76/6/26	***
Halton oscillatory ($\kappa = 10^6$)	108	4139	6.0×10^{-8}	+0.61	72/7/29	***
<i>C1: alternative operational configuration $(\beta, \gamma) = (2/3, 3/2)$</i>						
baseline ($\kappa = 1$)	108	2757	2.1×10^{-1}	+0.09	53/8/47	
moderate ($\kappa = 10^4$)	108	3775	8.7×10^{-6}	+0.50	71/8/29	***
progressive ($\kappa = 10^6$)	108	3589	1.3×10^{-4}	+0.42	69/8/31	***
extreme ($\kappa = 10^8$)	108	3712	6.0×10^{-5}	+0.44	67/7/34	***
spatial-thermal ($\kappa \approx 9 \times 10^4$)	108	3762	2.9×10^{-5}	+0.46	71/7/30	***
Sobol oscillatory ($\kappa = 10^6$)	108	3819	1.3×10^{-5}	+0.48	62/7/39	***
Sobol-digit osc. ($\kappa = 10^6$)	108	3653	1.3×10^{-4}	+0.42	67/7/34	***
Halton oscillatory ($\kappa = 10^6$)	108	4049	3.0×10^{-7}	+0.57	67/7/34	***
<i>Non-expansive regime $(\beta, \gamma) = (1/2, 1)$, covered by the convergence analysis</i>						
baseline ($\kappa = 1$)	108	2154	8.3×10^{-1}	-0.11	44/10/54	
moderate ($\kappa = 10^4$)	108	3965	4.0×10^{-6}	+0.51	71/6/31	***
progressive ($\kappa = 10^6$)	108	3662	1.2×10^{-4}	+0.42	66/7/35	***
extreme ($\kappa = 10^8$)	108	5009	9.2×10^{-16}	+0.91	92/6/10	***
spatial-thermal ($\kappa \approx 9 \times 10^4$)	108	3738	5.3×10^{-6}	+0.51	68/9/31	***
Sobol oscillatory ($\kappa = 10^6$)	108	5144	2.2×10^{-17}	+0.96	98/6/4	***
Sobol-digit osc. ($\kappa = 10^6$)	108	5060	2.3×10^{-16}	+0.93	93/6/9	***
Halton oscillatory ($\kappa = 10^6$)	108	5159	1.4×10^{-17}	+0.96	98/6/4	***

The especially large rank-biserial effects observed in the non-expansive regime for the *extreme* and oscillatory strategies have a natural geometric interpretation. When $\gamma = 1$, the physical-space DMS baseline cannot increase its step size after successful iterations, and therefore has little ability to compensate for a distorted coordinate system once the search starts contracting. Under strong scale heterogeneity, this makes the mismatch between physical step lengths and relative domain sizes particularly damaging. DMS-SI-Mix undergoes the same non-expansive dynamics

Table 2: DMS versus DMS-SI-Mix on the piezo-shunt benchmark ($\kappa \approx 1.4 \times 10^7$, $N_{\max} = 20\,000$ evaluations).

Algorithm	Evaluations	Pareto solutions	Hypervolume
DMS	20 001	5 990	92.83
DMS-SI-Mix (continuous block)	20 002	1 865	150.91

Table 3: Mixed-variable benchmark pairs. Each row reports the number of continuous, ordered discrete, and categorical coordinates in the mixed formulation, with the ranges of discrete cardinalities N_i and categorical cardinalities m_i .

Pair	q	n_C	n_D	n_K	N_i range	m_i range
(1) DPAM1 / DPAM1-Mix	2	4	3	3	[69, 123]	[32, 90]
(2) FES1 / FES1-Mix	2	4	3	3	[26, 98]	[24, 94]
(3) QV1 / QV1-Mix	2	4	3	3	[20, 36]	[20, 101]
(4) DTLZ2 / DTLZ2-Mix	3	4	4	4	[23, 56]	[44, 103]
(5) ZDT3 / ZDT3-Mix	2	10	10	10	[25, 104]	[27, 126]
(6) ZDT1 / ZDT1-Mix	2	10	10	10	[32, 129]	[21, 126]

in normalized coordinates, where a given value of α has the same fraction-of-domain meaning in every continuous variable. The larger effects in the conservative regime therefore reinforce, rather than weaken, the scale-invariance interpretation: removing expansion makes the scaling defect of the physical-space method more visible, since the expansion step is precisely what would otherwise let the physical-space method partially absorb a distorted coordinate system.

5.3. Piezoelectric shunt: an engineering instance

The piezoelectric shunt benchmark complements the synthetic suite with a single engineering instance. Decision variables include patch position, patch length, and shunt resistance, the last of which spans $[10^2, 10^6] \Omega$ and produces a contrast factor $\kappa \approx 1.4 \times 10^7$. Two objectives are minimized; the problem formulation and variable table are given in [Appendix A.4](#).

Within this single instance, DMS-SI-Mix attains a Hypervolume of 150.91 against 92.83 for DMS—a relative gap of 63% at identical budget—while producing fewer nondominated points (1 865 versus 5 990); the larger Hypervolume reflects coverage of a wider region of objective space, as visible in [Figure 3](#). We report this as a single applied test, not as additional statistical evidence: a one-instance result is consistent with the cross-strategy pattern of [Section 5.2](#) but does not by itself constitute one.

5.4. Mixed-variable benchmark pairs

The third block exercises the full mixed poll. Six benchmark pairs ([Table 3](#)) are solved in both a continuous formulation and a mixed formulation in which a subset of coordinates is replaced by ordered discrete or categorical variables while preserving the objective function. The pairs span convex, concave, disconnected, and three-objective fronts. Pairs (5) and (6) additionally carry a heterogeneous reparameterization of the continuous block, so the mixed formulation is exercised jointly with continuous-block scale heterogeneity; they should be read as combined stress tests of mixed structure and reparameterization, not as uniform mixed reformulations. Pair construction details are in [Appendix A.2](#).

Each pair is solved in both formulations under identical algorithmic parameters and a fixed pairwise Hypervolume reference point, so that HV values are directly comparable within a pair but not across pairs. IGD is reported where an analytical reference front exists (DTLZ2, ZDT3, ZDT1). CC_{vis} and DC_{vis} are computed on the cache of evaluated points, as defined in [Section 5.1](#).

The per-pair Pareto fronts are shown in [Figure 4](#). Two qualitative observations summarize the mixed-pair results, with the detailed comparison reproduced in [Appendix A.2](#).

(a) BASELINE, configuration C1.

(b) BASELINE, configuration C2.

(c) EXTREME, configuration C1.

(d) EXTREME, configuration C2.

Figure 2: Hypervolume performance profiles on the 108-benchmark continuous suite. **Top row** (BASELINE, $\kappa = 1$): under uniform scaling, DMS and the continuous block of DMS-SI-Mix attain statistically equivalent performance (Wilcoxon $r = -0.12$, $p = 0.85$), confirming algorithmic equivalence absent scale heterogeneity. **Bottom row** (EXTREME, $\kappa = 10^8$): under strong scale heterogeneity, DMS-SI-Mix dominates DMS across the entire τ range (Wilcoxon $r = +0.60$, C2; $r = +0.44$, C1). The two columns correspond to configurations C1 $(\beta, \gamma) = (2/3, 3/2)$ and C2 $(\beta, \gamma) = (1/2, 2)$, confirming that the contrast persists across step-size rules. Quantitative statistics for these and the remaining strategies are reported in Table 1.

Figure 3: Pareto front approximations on the piezo-shunt benchmark. DMS-SI-Mix extends the computed front towards lower values of f_1 , while DMS remains concentrated in a narrower region.

Figure 4: Pareto front approximations for the six benchmark pairs of Section 5.4, for the non-expansive regime $(\beta, \gamma) = (1/2, 1)$. Each panel overlays the continuous formulation (blue circles) and the mixed formulation (red squares); axes are objective values f_1, f_2 for the biobjective pairs and f_1, f_2, f_3 for the DTLZ2 pair. On ZDT1, DTLZ2, and ZDT3 the mixed front closely tracks the continuous front; on FES1, DPAM1, and QV1 a visible reduction in front coverage corresponds to the Hypervolume gap reported in Table 4.

Table 4: Results on mixed-variable benchmark pairs at $N_{\max} = 20000$ evaluations, for two step-size regimes: the non-expansive regime $(\beta, \gamma) = (1/2, 1)$ covered by Theorem 4.7, and the accelerated practical regime $(\beta, \gamma) = (1/2, 2)$ used in standard DMS implementations and not covered by the theorem. Hypervolume uses a fixed reference point per pair (directly comparable within a pair only); IGD is reported for pairs with an analytical reference front; CC_{vis} and DC_{vis} are computed over the cache of evaluated points of the mixed formulation, not over the final nondominated list.

Pair	Hypervolume		IGD		Coverage (mixed)	
	Continuous	Mixed	Continuous	Mixed	CC_{vis}	DC_{vis}
<i>Non-expansive regime $(\beta, \gamma) = (1/2, 1)$, covered by the convergence analysis</i>						
(1) DPAM1 / DPAM1-Mix	188.342	152.851	—	—	0.532	0.400
(2) FES1 / FES1-Mix	15.479	13.151	—	—	0.600	0.516
(3) QV1 / QV1-Mix	1.787	1.283	—	—	0.628	0.650
(4) DTLZ2 / DTLZ2-Mix	1.170	1.132	0.0278	0.0456	0.646	0.592
(5) ZDT3 / ZDT3-Mix	7.323	6.952	0.2692	0.5241	0.680	0.702
(6) ZDT1 / ZDT1-Mix	0.876	0.864	0.0009	0.0076	0.619	0.518
<i>Accelerated practical regime $(\beta, \gamma) = (1/2, 2)$</i>						
(1) DPAM1 / DPAM1-Mix	188.326	186.985	—	—	0.907	0.571
(2) FES1 / FES1-Mix	15.252	14.849	—	—	0.715	0.802
(3) QV1 / QV1-Mix	1.733	1.383	—	—	0.736	0.882
(4) DTLZ2 / DTLZ2-Mix	1.166	0.928	0.0310	0.1320	0.515	0.459
(5) ZDT3 / ZDT3-Mix	7.658	7.807	0.0803	0.0210	0.877	0.722
(6) ZDT1 / ZDT1-Mix	0.875	0.868	0.0016	0.0062	0.726	0.532

Non-expansive regime, $\gamma = 1$. At the conservative step-size regime covered by Theorem 4.7, the mixed formulation attains Hypervolume within a moderate multiplicative factor of the continuous baseline on pairs (1)–(4) (ratios in the range 0.72–0.97), with the largest relative gap on QV1 (1.283 versus 1.787, ratio 0.72) and the smallest on DTLZ2 (ratio 0.97). On the stress-test pairs (5) ZDT3-Mix and (6) ZDT1-Mix, which carry heterogeneous continuous-block reparameterization in addition to the mixed structure, the mixed formulation remains competitive (ratios 0.95 and 0.99). CC_{vis} and DC_{vis} on the cache lie in the ranges 0.53–0.68 and 0.40–0.70 respectively, confirming that the mixed poll exercises the combinatorial structure rather than collapsing to a continuous-only search.

Accelerated regime, $\gamma = 2$. The expansion regime increases the mixed-formulation Hypervolume on five of the six pairs and pushes their continuous-to-mixed ratio closer to one (e.g., DPAM1: 186.985 versus 188.326, ratio 0.99; FES1: 14.849 versus 15.252, ratio 0.97). The clear exception is (4) DTLZ2-Mix, where expansion lowers the mixed Hypervolume to 0.928 (from 1.132 under $\gamma = 1$) and worsens IGD to 0.1320 (from 0.0456), moving its continuous-to-mixed ratio away from one (to 0.80) rather than towards it; on pair (5) ZDT3-Mix the mixed formulation slightly exceeds the continuous baseline in Hypervolume (7.807 versus 7.658) while also reducing IGD (0.0210 versus 0.0803). Coverage on the cache rises in this regime, with CC_{vis} up to 0.907 (DPAM1-Mix) and DC_{vis} up to 0.882 (QV1-Mix). The theorem of Section 4 does not cover this regime, and we make no theoretical claim about it; the table reports the practical performance side by side with the $\gamma = 1$ figures so that the reader can compare the two without ambiguity.

The mixed-pair results, taken together with the continuous and engineering experiments, support the practical claim that DMS-SI-Mix is a usable solver across heterogeneous decision spaces under both conservative and accelerated step-size regimes. They do not, on their own, certify convergence: that role is played by the conditional certificate of Section 4.

6. Discussion and Extensions

This section places the results of Sections 4 and 5 in context, identifying the scope of the theory established here and the natural extensions of the framework.

6.1. Scope and limitations

The certificate of Section 4 applies to bound-constrained, deterministic, noise-free problems, and is conservative in three respects already stated within Section 4.3 and worth restating here in broader context.

The result is *conditional* on the existence of a refining subsequence (Assumption 4.1). Whether the projected canonical mixed-variable setting produces such a subsequence unconditionally is a globalization question that is not resolved by the classical direct-search analysis transported through the canonical map; we leave it to future work.

The continuous-block conclusion is Pareto–Clarke stationarity *along the fixed continuous polling directions*, not full Pareto–Clarke criticality. Strengthening this to a full Clarke statement would require asymptotically dense refining directions beyond the fixed positive spanning set of Assumption (A3), and is again outside the scope of the minimal certificate.

The finite-block conclusions are *weak* local Pareto optimality, meaning that no admissible rank-1 or single-coordinate move improves all objectives strictly (Definition 4.2). The certificate is silent about which integer fiber (\mathbf{k}^*, h^*) is reached: it characterizes the stationarity of whatever fiber the run lands on, without identifying a globally preferred one. This locality is consistent with direct-search methods, but is a real limitation when the finite-block landscape is rugged.

These three restrictions are explicit limitations of the present analysis, not hidden assumptions. The categorical-block conclusion relies on the covering property (Proposition B.1), which the Walecki-based schedule of Appendix B realizes; any deterministic schedule satisfying that property yields the same theoretical guarantees.

6.2. Extensions

Three natural extensions of DMS-SI-Mix follow from the canonical/real separation principle and do not affect the structure of the canonical search.

Constrained problems. General nonlinear constraints can be handled by standard direct-search constraint mechanisms [17, Sec. 13.1]—filter methods or extreme-barrier strategies—since constraints, like the objective, are evaluated in the real space Ω . The canonical search continues unchanged; only the acceptance test becomes constraint-aware.

Noisy or stochastic objectives. When F is noisy or stochastic, the acceptance criterion and the step-size update can be modified along the lines of derivative-free methods for noisy problems, but the canonical state, the reconstruction operator, and the mixed poll set remain unchanged. The separation principle isolates the source of stochasticity from the search geometry.

Surrogate-assisted search on expensive instances. For simulation-based applications with expensive evaluations, surrogate models can be introduced on the continuous block to guide the search without altering the treatment of the finite blocks. The mixed poll structure allows surrogates to coexist with intrinsic operators on the ordered discrete and categorical blocks.

Randomized permutation schedules, obtained by uniform sampling or Latin-hypercube constructions, fit within the framework and attain the covering property almost surely. We do not pursue them here in order to preserve full deterministic reproducibility, which is one of the design constraints of DMS-SI-Mix.

7. Conclusions

This paper introduced DMS-SI-Mix, a Direct Multisearch method for multiobjective optimization over heterogeneous decision spaces that combine continuous, ordered discrete, and categorical variables. The construction rests on a single structural device—the separation between a canonical search representation and a real evaluation space, mediated by a reconstruction operator that is a componentwise bijection (Lemma 2.5). A single resolution parameter α controls all three blocks through intrinsic neighborhood operators (continuous, rank-based discrete, identity-based categorical), and the method retains the DMS skeleton: nondominated list, complete polls, Pareto filtering, deterministic execution.

The canonical/real separation yields a sharp representation invariance result (Theorem 3.6): under affine continuous rescaling, order-preserving discrete relabeling, and arbitrary categorical relabeling, the canonical trajectory of DMS-SI-Mix is literally identical across representations, while the real iterates transform exactly as the representation map prescribes. The convergence certificate (Theorem 4.7) characterizes accumulation points of refining subsequences as mixed-block Pareto stationary, with a Pareto–Clarke condition on the continuous block and weak local Pareto optimality on the finite blocks. The result is deliberately conservative: it is conditional on the existence of a refining subsequence, restricted to fixed polling directions on the continuous block, and silent about which integer fiber a run reaches.

The numerical evaluation supports the practical claims associated with these structural properties. On 108 continuous benchmarks under eight scaling strategies, DMS-SI-Mix attains a Hypervolume advantage over standard DMS that is highly significant ($p < 0.001$, Wilcoxon) under every heterogeneous strategy and absent under uniform scaling—a threshold behavior consistent with the canonical-coordinate hypothesis. On a single engineering instance (piezoelectric shunt design, contrast factor $\kappa \approx 1.4 \times 10^7$), DMS-SI-Mix attains a 63% larger Hypervolume than DMS at identical budget. On six benchmark pairs combining all three variable types, the mixed formulation remains competitive with its continuous counterpart under both the non-expansive regime covered by the theory ($\gamma = 1$) and the accelerated practical regime ($\gamma = 2$), with empirical coverage diagnostics confirming that the mixed poll exercises the combinatorial structure rather than collapsing to a continuous-only search.

Future work targets the limitations identified in Section 6: a globalization theory establishing the unconditional existence of refining subsequences, the strengthening to full Clarke criticality under asymptotically dense refining directions, strong rather than weak local Pareto optimality on the finite blocks, and the extension of the convergence analysis to the success-expansion regime ($\gamma > 1$) used in standard DMS implementations and in the experiments of this paper.

Statements and Declarations

Funding. The author acknowledges the support of Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT), Portugal, through IDMEC, under LAETA, project UID/50022/2025.

Conflict of Interest. The author declares no financial or non-financial competing interests. The author co-authored the original Direct Multisearch (DMS) framework with A. L. Custódio, A. I. F. Vaz, and L. N. Vicente; the present work proposes an independent unified framework for heterogeneous-variable derivative-free optimization.

Data Availability. The benchmark suites used in this work are publicly available in a single open repository [19]. The continuous suite (Section 5.2) comprises 108 bound-constrained multiobjective problems, each instantiated under the eight scaling strategies of Appendix A.3. The mixed-variable suite (Section 5.4) provides self-contained wrappers for the corresponding mixed-variable instances, including the discrete grids, categorical encodings, and the six reported benchmark pairs. The repository also includes the base MATLAB problem definitions and index files documenting the generated instances.

Code Availability. The DMS-SI-Mix algorithm implementation in MATLAB will be made publicly available upon acceptance of this manuscript. The code is available to reviewers upon request during the review process.

Appendix A. Benchmark Construction and Supplementary Results

This appendix collects the construction of the benchmark suites used in Section 5 and the supplementary tables and figures referenced from there.

Appendix A.1. Continuous benchmark suite

The continuous suite used in Section 5.2 consists of 108 bound-constrained multiobjective benchmarks drawn from the standard DFO-MOO literature. The collection includes the ZDT family (ZDT1–ZDT4, ZDT6) [20], the DTLZ family [21], the WFG family [22], and the DPAM/FES/QV problems used in the original DMS study [1]. Dimensions range from $n = 2$ to $n = 30$ continuous variables, and objective counts are $q \in \{2, 3\}$. The full list of problems, with objective definitions and bounds, is published as an open MATLAB repository [19], which also hosts the mixed-variable suite of Appendix A.2.

Table A.5: Decision variables for the piezo-shunt benchmark ($\kappa \approx 1.4 \times 10^7$).

Variable	Description	Range	Units
$x_1 = p$	Patch position	[0.00, 0.50]	m
$x_2 = \ell$	Patch length	[0.01, 0.08]	m
$x_3 = R$	Shunt resistance	$[10^2, 10^6]$	Ω
$x_4 = L$	Shunt inductance	$[10^{-3}, 1]$	H

Appendix A.2. Mixed-variable benchmark pairs

The six benchmark pairs of Section 5.4 are built from the corresponding continuous benchmark by replacing a subset of coordinates with ordered discrete or categorical variables, following four construction principles. (i) *Objective preservation*: the objective function is always evaluated in the original continuous domain; ordered discrete variables are mapped to that domain by affine normalization, and categorical variables by fixed numeric embeddings. (ii) *Interleaving*: continuous, discrete, and categorical coordinates alternate in the decision vector following a fixed cyclic pattern C, K, D, C, D, K, . . . , ensuring that the three blocks contribute simultaneously to the local search geometry. (iii) *Heterogeneous cardinalities*: the discrete cardinalities N_i and categorical cardinalities m_i are chosen in the ranges of Table 3, with N_i, m_i varying across coordinates to avoid uniform structure. (iv) *Stress reparameterization on pairs (5)–(6)*: the continuous block of ZDT3-Mix and ZDT1-Mix carries a heterogeneous reparameterization that increases the contrast factor of the continuous component, so that the mixed formulation is exercised jointly with continuous-block scale heterogeneity. Detailed per-coordinate specifications, including the discrete grids V_i and categorical embeddings K_i , are distributed in the same open repository [19].

The per-pair Pareto front comparison is shown in Figure 4; the corresponding per-pair $CC_{\text{vis}}/DC_{\text{vis}}$ coverage diagnostics are reported in Table 4.

Appendix A.3. Scale transformation pipeline and supplementary tables

Each scaling strategy in Section 5.2 is a deterministic transformation of the bound vector $(\ell, u) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n$, designed to induce a controlled contrast factor

$$\kappa := \frac{\max_i(u_i - \ell_i)}{\min_i(u_i - \ell_i)}.$$

All strategies preserve the Pareto-front geometry: if $x \in \Omega$ is feasible in the original problem, the transformed point $T(x)$ is feasible in the rescaled problem with $F(T(x)) = F(x)$. The eight strategies are: *baseline*, identity ($\kappa = 1$); *moderate*, geometric stretch to $\kappa = 10^4$; *progressive*, geometric stretch to $\kappa = 10^6$; *extreme*, geometric stretch to $\kappa = 10^8$; *spatial-thermal*, physically motivated stretch with $\kappa \approx 9 \times 10^4$; and three *oscillatory* variants constructed from Sobol, Sobol-digit, and Halton low-discrepancy sequences at $\kappa = 10^6$, designed to test robustness to non-monotone scale heterogeneity. The per-strategy scaled instances generated by these transformations are distributed with the open repository [19].

Representative Hypervolume performance profiles are shown in Figure 2. The full per-strategy Hypervolume profiles $\pi(\tau)$ for configurations C1 and C2 underlie the cross-strategy summary reported in Table 1.

Appendix A.4. Piezoelectric shunt benchmark

The piezoelectric shunt benchmark of Section 5.3 is a two-objective design problem for vibration suppression of a thin elastic structure equipped with a piezoelectric patch and a resistive shunt circuit. The two objectives minimize the residual vibration amplitude at the first resonance and the steady-state energy dissipated in the shunt resistor.

The variables span $[0, 0.5]$ for p , $[0.01, 0.08]$ for ℓ , $[10^2, 10^6]$ for R , and $[10^{-3}, 1]$ for L (Table A.5). The contrast factor between the widest and narrowest variable range is $\kappa = (10^6 - 10^2)/(0.08 - 0.01) \approx 1.4 \times 10^7$, which is the heterogeneity that makes the benchmark a relevant scale-test. Both algorithms use the same evaluation budget $N_{\text{max}} = 20\,000$ and the same initial design point; DMS-SI-Mix runs in normalized coordinates, while DMS runs in the physical scaled space.

Appendix B. CC-DNR Permutation Schedules and Walecki Covering Cycles

This appendix specifies the deterministic neighborhood-rotation schedule used in the categorical block of DMS-SI-Mix and records its coverage property. The construction is the classical *covering-cycles* schedule after Walecki, fully specified below; we include the finite coverage argument needed for the present convergence analysis, resting on the classical Hamilton decomposition of K_{m_i} [23]. A more general treatment of transient categorical geometries and related coverage schedules is developed in the companion work [16]. Here we record the statements relied upon in Sections 3.2, 4, and 5.

Appendix B.1. Rank-one graphs and covering property

Fix $i \in \mathcal{I}_K$ and write $m := m_i$. For a permutation $\pi \in S_m$, the *rank-one graph* $G(\pi)$ has vertex set K_i and edges

$$E(G(\pi)) = \{\{\pi(j), \pi(j')\} : j' \equiv j + 1 \pmod{m}, j, j' \in \{1, \dots, m\}\}.$$

$G(\pi)$ is the Hamiltonian cycle traced by π on the category set. By Definition 3.3, two categories $c, c' \in K_i$ are rank-one categorical neighbors under π , at any resolution with $r_i^K(\alpha) = 1$, if and only if $\{c, c'\} \in E(G(\pi))$. Coverage of all unordered pairs of categories by rank-one neighborhoods over the rotation period therefore amounts to covering all edges of the complete graph K_m by the union of the Hamiltonian cycles $\{G(\pi_i^{(e)}) : e = 0, \dots, P_i - 1\}$.

Proposition B.1 (Coverage of the covering-cycles schedule). *The covering-cycles schedule $\Pi_i^{\text{cov}} = \{\pi_i^{(e)}\}_{e \geq 0}$ defined below has period $P_i = \lceil (m_i - 1)/2 \rceil$ and satisfies the following covering property: for every pair of distinct categories $c, c' \in K_i$, there exists a residue $e^*(i, c, c') \in \{0, \dots, P_i - 1\}$ such that c and c' are rank-one cyclic neighbors under $\pi_i^{(e^*)}$. The bound $P_i = \lceil (m_i - 1)/2 \rceil$ is tight: no deterministic schedule attains coverage of all pairs in strictly fewer than $\lceil (m_i - 1)/2 \rceil$ distinct permutations.*

The tightness of P_i follows by counting: each permutation of length m exposes at most m rank-one cyclic adjacencies (exactly m when $m \geq 3$), so E distinct permutations expose at most $E \cdot m$ pairs; covering all $\binom{m}{2} = m(m-1)/2$ pairs therefore requires $E \geq (m-1)/2$, hence $E \geq \lceil (m-1)/2 \rceil$. The existence claim — that the schedule below realizes the bound — follows from the constructions of the next subsection.

Appendix B.2. Construction of the schedule

The schedule Π_i^{cov} is defined separately for odd m , even m , and the boundary case $m = 2$. We give each construction and then prove the covering property in a self-contained way.

Boundary case $m = 2$. The complete graph K_2 has a single edge; the schedule reduces to a single permutation $\pi_i^{(0)} = \text{id}$, the only permutation up to relabeling, with $P_i = 1$.

Odd case, $m = 2\mu + 1$. Identify K_i with $\{\infty\} \cup \mathbb{Z}_{2\mu}$, where ∞ is a distinguished pivot. The base *zig-zag word* $u^{(0)} \in (\mathbb{Z}_{2\mu})^{2\mu}$ is

$$u^{(0)} = (0, 1, -1, 2, -2, \dots, \mu, -(\mu - 1)) \pmod{2\mu},$$

listing each element of $\mathbb{Z}_{2\mu}$ exactly once. For $e \in \{0, \dots, \mu - 1\}$, the rotated word $u_\ell^{(e)} := (u_\ell^{(0)} + e) \pmod{2\mu}$ defines the permutation

$$\pi_i^{(e)} = (\infty, u_1^{(e)}, u_2^{(e)}, \dots, u_{2\mu}^{(e)}).$$

The Hamiltonian cycles $G(\pi_i^{(0)}), \dots, G(\pi_i^{(\mu-1)})$ are pairwise edge-disjoint and partition $E(K_m)$, with $P_i = \mu = (m-1)/2$. This is the classical Walecki rotation construction.

Even case, $m = 2\mu$. K_m decomposes into $\mu - 1$ edge-disjoint Hamiltonian cycles $C_0, \dots, C_{\mu-2}$ and a perfect matching M :

$$E(K_m) = E(C_0) \dot{\cup} E(C_1) \dot{\cup} \dots \dot{\cup} E(C_{\mu-2}) \dot{\cup} M.$$

Each C_e gives a permutation $\pi_i^{(e)}$ with $G(\pi_i^{(e)}) = C_e$ for $e = 0, \dots, \mu - 2$. The matching M is rank-one-encoded by a single additional permutation $\pi_i^{(\mu-1)}$ whose rank-one cyclic adjacencies include every edge of M ; this permutation is constructed explicitly in the proof of the covering property below. The period is $P_i = \mu = m/2$, matching $\lceil (m - 1)/2 \rceil$ for even m .

Proof of the covering property in Proposition B.1. By the rank-one graph identity of Appendix B.1, two categories are rank-one neighbours under π exactly when they are adjacent in the Hamiltonian cycle $G(\pi)$; covering every pair of categories is therefore equivalent to covering every edge of K_m by the rank-one graphs $\{G(\pi_i^{(e)})\}_{e=0}^{P_i-1}$.

Odd $m = 2\mu + 1$. The complete graph $K_{2\mu+1}$ admits a decomposition into μ edge-disjoint Hamiltonian cycles [23], realized explicitly by the zig-zag rotation above: the cycles $G(\pi_i^{(0)}), \dots, G(\pi_i^{(\mu-1)})$ are pairwise edge-disjoint and their union is $E(K_m)$. Hence every pair $\{c, c'\}$ lies in exactly one $G(\pi_i^{(e)})$ and is exposed as a rank-one neighbour under $\pi_i^{(e)}$. The period is $P_i = \mu = (m - 1)/2 = \lceil (m - 1)/2 \rceil$.

Even $m = 2\mu$. Here $K_{2\mu}$ decomposes into $\mu - 1$ edge-disjoint Hamiltonian cycles $C_0, \dots, C_{\mu-2}$ and a perfect matching M [23]. The cycles give $\pi_i^{(0)}, \dots, \pi_i^{(\mu-2)}$ with $G(\pi_i^{(e)}) = C_e$, covering $E(K_m) \setminus M$. Writing $M = \{\{a_1, b_1\}, \dots, \{a_\mu, b_\mu\}\}$ with the 2μ endpoints distinct, the Hamiltonian cycle

$$a_1, b_1, a_2, b_2, \dots, a_\mu, b_\mu, a_1$$

contains every matching edge $\{a_k, b_k\}$; let $\pi_i^{(\mu-1)}$ be the permutation tracing it. Then $M \subseteq E(G(\pi_i^{(\mu-1)}))$, so the edges of M —the only ones left uncovered—are exposed under $\pi_i^{(\mu-1)}$. The period is $P_i = \mu = m/2 = \lceil (m - 1)/2 \rceil$.

Boundary $m = 2$. K_2 has a single edge, exposed by $\pi_i^{(0)} = \text{id}$, so $P_i = 1 = \lceil (m - 1)/2 \rceil$.

In every case the union of the rank-one graphs is $E(K_m)$, which is the covering property; the counting argument following Proposition B.1 shows that no schedule attains it with fewer than $\lceil (m - 1)/2 \rceil$ permutations, so P_i is tight. \square

Appendix B.3. Worked example: identity versus position under rotation

The separation of canonical identity from position under the active permutation, which keeps the cache consistent across rotations, is best seen on a concrete instance. Let $m_i = 5$, write categories as $\{A_1, \dots, A_5\}$ with canonical-identity $A_j \leftrightarrow h_i = j$, and consider the target $h_i^* = 5$ at a resolution with $r_i^K(\alpha) = 1$.

Permutation $\pi = (1, 2, 3, 4, 5)$ (identity). The position of A_5 is $j^* = \pi^{-1}(5) = 5$. The rank-one cyclic neighbors are at positions $j^* \pm 1 \pmod{5} = \{1, 4\}$, with identities $\pi(1) = 1, \pi(4) = 4$, that is, $\{A_1, A_4\}$.

Permutation $\pi' = (1, 2, 5, 4, 3)$. Now $j^* = (\pi')^{-1}(5) = 3$, with cyclic neighbors at positions $\{2, 4\}$ and identities $\pi'(2) = 2, \pi'(4) = 4$, that is, $\{A_2, A_4\}$.

Cache consequence. Across the two permutations, the position of A_5 changes (5 versus 3) and its rank-one neighborhood changes ($\{A_1, A_4\}$ versus $\{A_2, A_4\}$). The canonical identity is invariant: $A_5 \leftrightarrow h_i = 5$ under both. The cache entry indexed by $h_i = 5$ is therefore reusable across permutations, sparing fresh objective evaluations. This is the operational content of the separation between identity and position emphasized in Section 3.2: identity is a property of the canonical state and persists across rotations; position is a property of the neighborhood operator and varies with the schedule.

Appendix C. Technical Proofs

This appendix collects the proofs deferred from Sections 3 and 4. The logical dependency structure of the convergence argument—how the standing assumptions, the refining-subsequence hypothesis, and the three block-level results combine into Theorem 4.7—is summarized in Figure C.5.

Figure C.5: Logical dependency structure of the convergence analysis. Solid arrows denote primary proof dependence; dashed arrows denote the common refining subsequence supplied by Assumption 4.1. The diagram records the main dependencies among the principal assumptions, block results, and the final theorem; auxiliary local lemmas and routine transfer steps are omitted for readability. The covering property (Proposition B.1) is used exclusively in the categorical block (Proposition 4.5). Theorem 4.7 combines the three block results.

Appendix C.1. Proof of Theorem 3.6

Proof of Theorem 3.6. We first verify the factorization $\Psi' = T \circ \Psi$. Each representation change (a)–(c) renames the real domain without altering the canonical space Ξ or the canonical coordinates. Under (a), the i -th continuous component of Ψ' is $y_i \mapsto a_i(\ell_i + (u_i - \ell_i)y_i) + b_i$, which is exactly T composed with the i -th component of Ψ ; the canonical coordinate $y_i \in [0, 1]$ and the continuous neighborhood operator N^C (Definition 3.1) are unaffected. Under (b), the lookup $k_i \mapsto v_{i,k_i}$ is replaced by $k_i \mapsto v'_{i,k_i}$, while the index k_i itself and the discrete rank $r_i^D(\alpha)$ are unchanged. Under (c), the lookup $h_i \mapsto c_{i,h_i}$ is replaced by $h_i \mapsto c'_{i,h_i}$, while the canonical identity h_i and the categorical neighborhood operator N_i^K —which acts on $\{1, \dots, m_i\}$ through the active permutation—are unaffected. In each case the transformed reconstruction is the original reconstruction followed by the relabeling, so $\Psi' = T \circ \Psi$.

We now prove $\xi'_t = \xi_t$ and $\mathcal{L}'_t = \mathcal{L}_t$ by induction on the iteration index t , comparing the run on F with the run on F' . Throughout, primed quantities refer to the run on F' .

Base case. By hypothesis, the two runs use identical initialization in canonical coordinates, so $\mathcal{L}'_0 = \mathcal{L}_0$ and every canonical state and step size in the initial list coincides; in particular $\xi'_0 = \xi_0$.

Inductive step. Suppose $\mathcal{L}'_t = \mathcal{L}_t$, so that the two runs hold identical lists of canonical entries at iteration t . The poll center is selected by a deterministic rule applied to identical canonical lists with identical objective values (the selection rule of Section 2.2 may consult any combination of canonical entries, objective values, and iteration index, all of which coincide across the two runs); hence both runs select the same entry, with the same canonical state $\xi'_t = \xi_t$ and step size $\alpha'_t = \alpha_t$. The mixed poll set $\mathcal{P}(\xi_t, \alpha_t)$ depends only on ξ_t, α_t , and the active permutation schedule (Definition 3.4), all identical across the two runs; both runs therefore generate the same set of canonical trial states.

For every canonical state $\xi \in \Xi$, the factorization $\Psi' = T \circ \Psi$ and the definition of the pullback give

$$F'(\Psi'(\xi)) = F'(T(\Psi(\xi))) = F(T^{-1}(T(\Psi(\xi)))) = F(\Psi(\xi)),$$

so each trial state carries the same objective vector in the two runs. All Pareto-dominance and acceptance comparisons (Definition 2.7) therefore yield identical outcomes; the poll is successful in one run if and only if it is successful in the other, and the list update produces the same canonical list: $\mathcal{L}'_{t+1} = \mathcal{L}_{t+1}$. The step-size update of equation (4) depends only on whether the poll is successful, so it too coincides; the categorical rotation-counter update depends only on the canonical state, the poll step size, and the success flag, all of which agree, so the active permutation schedules continue to agree at iteration $t + 1$. This completes the induction.

Finally, $x'_t = T(x_t)$ follows by applying Ψ' to the common canonical state: by $\Psi' = T \circ \Psi$ and $\xi'_t = \xi_t$, $x'_t = \Psi'(\xi'_t) = T(\Psi(\xi_t)) = T(x_t)$. \square

Appendix C.2. Auxiliary results

The block-level proofs below rely on two auxiliary results that we state in compact form. Both are proved in full below; the broader theory is developed in the companion work [16].

Proposition C.1 (Simultaneous rank-one refinement). *Let*

$$\alpha^* := \min\left\{\min_{i \in \mathcal{I}_D} \frac{3}{2(N_i-1)}, \min_{i \in \mathcal{I}_K} \frac{3}{2m_i}\right\} > 0.$$

For every $\alpha < \alpha^$, both finite ranks satisfy $r_i^D(\alpha) = 1$ for all $i \in \mathcal{I}_D$ and $r_i^K(\alpha) = 1$ for all $i \in \mathcal{I}_K$; in the continuous block, the canonical step magnitude equals α and therefore tends to zero with α .*

Proof. Using $\text{round}(x) \leq 1 \Leftrightarrow x < 3/2$, the formulas (5) and (6) give $r_i^D(\alpha) = 1$ iff $\alpha < 3/(2(N_i - 1))$ and $r_i^K(\alpha) = 1$ iff $\alpha < 3/(2m_i)$. The minimum over the finite index sets is $\alpha^* > 0$ by (A1). \square

Lemma C.2 (Rejection-to-limit on a fixed fiber). *Let $\mathcal{T}' \subseteq \mathcal{T}$ be infinite with $\alpha_t \rightarrow 0$ and the finite blocks frozen at (\mathbf{k}^*, h^*) , and let y^* be an accumulation point of $\{y_t\}_{t \in \mathcal{T}'}$. Let ξ_{mod}^* be obtained from $\xi^* = (y^*, \mathbf{k}^*, h^*)$ by modifying a single finite-block coordinate, and let ξ_t^{mod} denote the same modification applied to ξ_t . If, for all sufficiently large $t \in \mathcal{T}'$, $\xi_t^{\text{mod}} \in \mathcal{P}(\xi_t, \alpha_t)$ and iteration t is unsuccessful, then there exists $\ell^* \in \{1, \dots, q\}$ with $F_{\ell^*}(\Psi(\xi_{\text{mod}}^*)) \geq F_{\ell^*}(\Psi(\xi^*))$.*

Proof. Fix $t \in \mathcal{T}'$ large enough that the stated inclusion and unsuccessfulness hold. Since the poll is complete and iteration t is unsuccessful, processing all trials leaves the list unchanged, $\mathcal{L}_t^+ = \mathcal{L}_t$. The poll center is itself an entry of \mathcal{L}_t .

We claim $F(\Psi(\xi_t^{\text{mod}})) \not\prec F(\Psi(\xi_t))$. Suppose, for contradiction, that $F(\Psi(\xi_t^{\text{mod}})) < F(\Psi(\xi_t))$; that is, the trial ξ_t^{mod} Pareto-dominates the poll center. We distinguish whether ξ_t^{mod} is acceptable in the sense of Definition 2.7.

If ξ_t^{mod} is not acceptable, then some entry $(\xi_c, \alpha_c, F_c) \in \mathcal{L}_t$ Pareto-dominates it, $F_c < F(\Psi(\xi_t^{\text{mod}}))$. By transitivity of $<$, $F_c < F(\Psi(\xi_t))$, so entry c dominates the poll center; this contradicts the nondominance of \mathcal{L}_t when c is distinct from the center, and the irreflexivity of $<$ when it is not.

If ξ_t^{mod} is acceptable, the processing rule of Definition 2.7 inserts it and removes every entry it dominates. Two subcases arise. Either ξ_t^{mod} coincides canonically with an existing entry $(\xi_b, \alpha_b, F_b) \in \mathcal{L}_t$, in which case $F_b = F(\Psi(\xi_t^{\text{mod}})) < F(\Psi(\xi_t))$ with b distinct from the center—the modification alters a finite-block coordinate, so $\xi_t^{\text{mod}} \neq \xi_t$ canonically—again contradicting nondominance; or ξ_t^{mod} is canonically new, and its insertion removes the poll center (which it dominates), so $\mathcal{L}_t^+ \neq \mathcal{L}_t$, contradicting the unsuccessfulness of iteration t .

In every case we reach a contradiction, so $F(\Psi(\xi_t^{\text{mod}})) \not\prec F(\Psi(\xi_t))$.

By the definition of $<$, $F(\Psi(\xi_t^{\text{mod}})) \not\prec F(\Psi(\xi_t))$ means there exists $\ell_t \in \{1, \dots, q\}$ with $F_{\ell_t}(\Psi(\xi_t^{\text{mod}})) \geq F_{\ell_t}(\Psi(\xi_t))$. Since y^* is an accumulation point of $\{y_t\}_{t \in \mathcal{T}'}$, first restrict \mathcal{T}' to an infinite subset along which $y_t \rightarrow y^*$; since q is finite, pass to a further infinite subset on which $\ell_t \equiv \ell^*$ is constant. The finite blocks are frozen at (\mathbf{k}^*, h^*) , so $\xi_t \rightarrow \xi^*$ and $\xi_t^{\text{mod}} \rightarrow \xi_{\text{mod}}^*$ in the only varying (continuous) coordinates. The fiber map $F_{\ell^*} \circ \Psi$ is continuous by Assumption (A2); passing to the limit in $F_{\ell^*}(\Psi(\xi_t^{\text{mod}})) \geq F_{\ell^*}(\Psi(\xi_t))$ yields $F_{\ell^*}(\Psi(\xi_{\text{mod}}^*)) \geq F_{\ell^*}(\Psi(\xi^*))$. \square

Appendix C.3. Proof of Proposition 4.3

Proof sketch. Let \mathcal{T} , (\mathbf{k}^*, h^*) , and y^* be as in Proposition 4.3. Set $G_\ell := (F_{\mathbf{k}^*, h^*})_\ell$; each G_ℓ is locally Lipschitz on $[0, 1]^{nc}$ by (A2). Fix a polling direction $d \in \mathcal{D}_C$ feasible at y^* and let $\mathcal{T}(d) \subseteq \mathcal{T}$ be an infinite subset along which $y_t \rightarrow y^*$. Three steps then yield the conclusion.

Step 1: per-direction inequality. For $t \in \mathcal{T}(d)$ large enough, the projection onto $[0, 1]^{nc}$ in Definition 3.1 is inactive at the trial $y_t + \alpha_t d$, since $\alpha_t \rightarrow 0$ and d is feasible at y^* . Unsuccessfulness of the poll then forces, for some $\ell_t \in \{1, \dots, q\}$, $G_{\ell_t}(y_t + \alpha_t d) \geq G_{\ell_t}(y_t)$, by an argument analogous to Lemma C.2 applied to a continuous trial.

Step 2: passage to the Clarke derivative. Passing to a further subsequence on which ℓ_t is constantly some ℓ , the inequality $G_\ell(y_t + \alpha_t d) \geq G_\ell(y_t)$, combined with local Lipschitz continuity of G_ℓ and the definition of the Clarke generalized directional derivative as a lim sup of difference quotients, yields $G_\ell^\circ(y^*; d) \geq 0$.

Step 3: conclusion. Since $d \in \mathcal{D}_C$ feasible at y^* was arbitrary, the inequality holds for every such d , which is the Pareto–Clarke stationarity condition (Si). The two auxiliary facts used here—preservation of the Clarke generalized directional derivative under the affine canonical pullback, and eventual feasibility of a feasible polling direction for small α —are standard in direct-search Clarke analysis [18, 17]. \square

Appendix C.4. Proof of Proposition 4.4

Proof. Fix $i \in \mathcal{I}_D$ and $k'_i \in \{k_i^* - 1, k_i^* + 1\} \cap \{1, \dots, N_i\}$, and set $\mathcal{T}' := \{t \in \mathcal{T} : \alpha_t < \alpha^*\}$, which is cofinite in \mathcal{T} because $\alpha_t \rightarrow 0$. By Proposition C.1, $r_i^D(\alpha_t) = 1$ for every $t \in \mathcal{T}'$, so both feasible adjacent indices $k_i^* \pm 1$ lie in $\mathcal{P}(\xi_t, \alpha_t)$. The trial $\xi_t[k_i \leftarrow k'_i]$ is therefore in the mixed poll set; Lemma C.2 applied to the modification $k_i \leftarrow k'_i$ supplies the index ℓ^* and the inequality. \square

Appendix C.5. Proof of Proposition 4.5

Proof. Fix $i \in \mathcal{I}_K$ and $h'_i \neq h_i^*$. By the covering property of the CC-DNR schedule (Appendix B), there is a rotation residue $e^* = e^*(i, h_i^*, h'_i) \in \{0, \dots, P_i - 1\}$ such that the permutation $\pi_i^{(e^*)}$ exposes h'_i as a rank-1 neighbor of h_i^* . By the center-local rotation rule (Section 3.2) and the fairness of poll-center selection (A5), the persistent entry j^* encounters the residue e^* in coordinate i along an infinite subset $\mathcal{T}'(i, e^*) \subseteq \mathcal{T}$. On $\mathcal{T}'(i, e^*)$, $\alpha_t \rightarrow 0$ eventually gives $r_i^K(\alpha_t) = 1$ (Proposition C.1), so h'_i is a rank-1 categorical neighbor of h_i^* under the active permutation; the trial $\xi_t[h_i \leftarrow h'_i]$ therefore lies in $\mathcal{P}(\xi_t, \alpha_t)$. Lemma C.2 applied to the modification $h_i \leftarrow h'_i$ supplies the index ℓ^* and the inequality. \square

Appendix C.6. Proof of Theorem 4.7

Proof. By Assumption 4.1, the finite blocks are frozen at (\mathbf{k}^*, h^*) on \mathcal{T} , and the step sizes α_t tend to zero on \mathcal{T} . Compactness of $[0, 1]^{nc}$ yields an accumulation point y^* of $\{y_t\}_{t \in \mathcal{T}}$; set $\xi^* := (y^*, \mathbf{k}^*, h^*)$ and $x^* := \Psi(\xi^*) \in \Omega$. Propositions 4.3, 4.4, and 4.5 establish conditions (Si), (Sii), and (Siii) of Definition 4.6, respectively, so ξ^* is mixed-block Pareto stationary; the bijectivity of Ψ (Lemma 2.5) transfers the conclusion to x^* . The modular structure—one block at a time, each with its own intrinsic notion of local optimality—is essential: no global variational structure is imposed across the heterogeneous decision space. \square

Appendix D. Implementation Details

This appendix collects implementation-level details that are used by the reference DMS-SI-Mix implementation in the experiments of Section 5. None of them affects the algorithm’s behavior in exact arithmetic; they specify how the algorithm is realized in finite-precision MATLAB.

Table D.6: Default algorithmic parameters of the reference DMS-SI-Mix implementation. The continuous polling set $\mathcal{D}_C = \{\pm e_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}_C}$ is the canonical one-coordinate-at-a-time choice, which yields $|\mathcal{P}_C(\xi, \alpha)| \leq 2n_C$ continuous trials per poll.

Parameter	Value	Notes
α_0 (initial resolution)	0.1	in canonical units
τ (cache match tolerance)	10^{-8}	continuous block only
(β, γ) , config C1	(2/3, 3/2)	moderate operational
(β, γ) , config C2	(1/2, 2)	default of public DMS
(β, γ) , non-expansive	(1/2, 1)	covered by Thm 4.7
\mathcal{D}_C	$\{\pm e_i\}$	coordinate directions
Categorical schedule	covering cycles	Appendix B
Rotation counter	$\rho_{i,j}$	center-local; no global epoch
N_{\max} (evaluation budget)	20 000	all experiments

Appendix D.1. Canonical state representation and cache

A canonical state $\xi = (y, \mathbf{k}, h)$ is stored as a single structured record with three fields: $y \in [0, 1]^{n_C}$ as a double-precision vector, $\mathbf{k} \in \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}_D} \{1, \dots, N_i\}$ as an integer vector, and $h \in \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}_K} \{1, \dots, m_i\}$ as an integer vector of identity indices. The reconstruction operator Ψ is a single componentwise function call; no representation conversion takes place inside the polling loop.

The cache C (Definition 2.6) is realized as a hash table keyed by a fingerprint of ξ that quantizes the continuous block at a tolerance $\tau = 10^{-8}$ (each continuous canonical coordinate is rounded to the nearest multiple of τ) and concatenates the result with the integer finite-block indices. Two canonical states with the same fingerprint produce the same cache entry; canonical states whose fingerprints differ trigger a fresh evaluation. The convergence analysis of Section 4 assumes exact canonical matching, so τ is an implementation parameter introduced for floating-point robustness and not a quantity that appears in any of the theoretical statements. In the experiments of Section 5, cache reuse is observed, particularly on mixed-variable problems where the finite-block coordinates of the canonical space concentrate trial points on discrete strata.

Appendix D.2. Initialization

The initial list \mathcal{L}_0 is built from a single deterministic starting point in the real decision space Ω , constructed by the *line/center* rule: the continuous coordinates are placed at the midpoint of their canonical box, $y_i = 0.5$ for $i \in \mathcal{I}_C$; each ordered discrete coordinate is placed at its middle rank, $k_i = \lceil N_i/2 \rceil$ for $i \in \mathcal{I}_D$; and each categorical coordinate is placed at its first identity, $h_i = 1$ for $i \in \mathcal{I}_K$. In the scale-invariance study of Section 5.2, both algorithms additionally support multi-point Halton-sequence initialization for the starting set when the comparison protocol calls for it; the Halton points are also defined in the canonical box and then reconstructed to Ω .

Appendix D.3. Default algorithmic parameters

Table D.6 lists the default parameters used by DMS-SI-Mix in the numerical experiments. The two configurations C1 and C2 differ only in (β, γ) and correspond, respectively, to a moderate-step operational comparison and to the standard configuration of public Direct Multisearch implementations.

No hypervolume gate is applied: the step-size update in all reported runs is the operational rule of (4), not the gated variant referenced in Section 2.2. The categorical permutation is indexed by the rank-one rotation counter $\rho_{i,j}$ defined in Section 3.2; there is no global epoch-length parameter, so the schedule of any list entry depends only on its own history of rank-one-regime unsuccessful polls.

References

- [1] A. L. Custódio, J. F. A. Madeira, A. I. F. Vaz, L. N. Vicente, Direct multisearch for multiobjective optimization, *SIAM Journal on Optimization* 21 (3) (2011) 1109–1140. doi:10.1137/10079731X.

- [2] A. L. Custódio, J. F. A. Madeira, A. I. F. Vaz, L. N. Vicente, Errata to “Direct multisearch for multiobjective optimization”, <http://www.mat.uc.pt/~lnv/papers/errata-dms.pdf>, errata to *SIAM J. Optim.* **21** (2011) 1109–1140.
- [3] J. Bignon, S. Le Digabel, L. Salomon, DMulti-MADS: mesh adaptive direct multisearch for bound-constrained blackbox multiobjective optimization, *Computational Optimization and Applications* **79** (2) (2021) 301–338.
- [4] M. A. Abramson, C. Audet, J. W. Chrissis, J. G. Walston, Mesh adaptive direct search algorithms for mixed variable optimization, *Optimization Letters* **3** (1) (2009) 35–47.
- [5] C. Audet, J. E. Dennis, Jr., Mesh adaptive direct search algorithms for constrained optimization, *SIAM Journal on Optimization* **17** (1) (2006) 188–217.
- [6] C. Audet, E. Hallé-Hannan, S. Le Digabel, C. Tribes, CatMADS: Mesh adaptive direct search for constrained blackbox optimization with categorical variables, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.06937>, arXiv:2506.06937 (2025).
- [7] R. Hamano, M. Nomura, S. Saito, K. Uchida, S. Shirakawa, CatCMA with margin: Stochastic optimization for continuous, integer, and categorical variables, in: *Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference (GECCO '25)*, ACM, 2025, pp. 737–745.
- [8] J. Pelamatti, L. Brevault, M. Balesdent, E.-G. Talbi, Y. Guerin, Efficient global optimization of constrained mixed variable problems, *Journal of Global Optimization* **73** (3) (2019) 583–613.
- [9] J. Müller, C. A. Shoemaker, R. Piché, SO-MI: A surrogate model algorithm for computationally expensive nonlinear mixed-integer black-box global optimization problems, *Computers & Operations Research* **40** (5) (2013) 1383–1400. doi:10.1016/j.cor.2012.08.022.
- [10] J. Larson, M. Menickelly, S. M. Wild, Derivative-free optimization methods, *Acta Numerica* **28** (2019) 287–404.
- [11] C. Audet, W. Hare, *Derivative-Free and Blackbox Optimization*, Springer Series in Operations Research and Financial Engineering, Springer, 2017.
- [12] K. J. Dzahini, F. Rinaldi, C. W. Royer, D. Zeffiro, Direct-search methods in the year 2025: Theoretical guarantees and algorithmic paradigms, *EURO Journal on Computational Optimization* **13** (2025) 100110. doi:10.1016/j.ejco.2025.100110.
- [13] J. F. A. Madeira, GLODS-SI: Scale-invariant global-local direct search for engineering design optimization, *Journal of Computational Design and Engineering* (2026). doi:10.1093/jcde/qwag049.
- [14] J. F. A. Madeira, GLODS-SI-Mix: Scale-invariant global-local direct search for mixed-variable single-objective optimization, Submitted, companion work (2026).
- [15] J. F. A. Madeira, Deterministic neighborhood rotation (dnr) for categorical variables in derivative-free optimization, Preprint, companion work; available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19257923> (2026). doi:10.5281/zenodo.19257923.
- [16] J. F. A. Madeira, Mixed-variable optimisation as a metric product space: Transient categorical geometry and a hierarchy of local optimality, Preprint, companion work; available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18704776> (2026). doi:10.5281/zenodo.18704776.
- [17] A. R. Conn, K. Scheinberg, L. N. Vicente, *Introduction to Derivative-Free Optimization*, MPS-SIAM Series on Optimization, SIAM, Philadelphia, PA, 2009.
- [18] F. H. Clarke, *Optimization and Nonsmooth Analysis*, Classics in Applied Mathematics, SIAM, Philadelphia, 1990, reissue of the 1983 Wiley edition. doi:10.1137/1.9781611971309.

- [19] J. F. A. Madeira, [MOO_Prob_Matlab: Continuous and mixed-variable MATLAB benchmark suites for multiobjective optimization](#), GitHub repository, version 1.0.0, accompanying the DMS-SI-Mix manuscript (2026). URL https://github.com/aguilarmadeira/MOO_Prob_Matlab
- [20] E. Zitzler, K. Deb, L. Thiele, Comparison of multiobjective evolutionary algorithms: empirical results, *Evolutionary Computation* 8 (2) (2000) 173–195. doi:10.1162/106365600568202.
- [21] K. Deb, L. Thiele, M. Laumanns, E. Zitzler, Scalable test problems for evolutionary multiobjective optimization, in: A. Abraham, L. Jain, R. Goldberg (Eds.), *Evolutionary Multiobjective Optimization*, Advanced Information and Knowledge Processing, Springer, London, 2005, pp. 105–145. doi:10.1007/1-84628-137-7_6.
- [22] S. Huband, P. Hingston, L. Barone, L. While, A review of multiobjective test problems and a scalable test problem toolkit, *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 10 (5) (2006) 477–506. doi:10.1109/TEVC.2005.861417.
- [23] B. Alspach, J.-C. Bermond, D. Sotteau, Decomposition into cycles I: Hamilton decompositions, in: G. Hahn, G. Sabidussi, R. E. Woodrow (Eds.), *Cycles and Rays*, Vol. 301 of NATO ASI Series C: Mathematical and Physical Sciences, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, 1990, pp. 9–18.